

From Sense to Sound: Mapping High-Level Sonic Percepts to Sound Generation

by Sylvain Le Groux

Submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirement for
the degree of Diploma of Advanced Studies
Doctorate in Computer Science and Digital Communications
Department of Technology

Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Barcelona

TUTOR: PR. XAVIER SERRA

30th August 2006

Contents

1	INTRODUCTION	17
1.1	Motivation	17
1.2	Context	19
1.2.1	Interdisciplinarity	19
1.2.2	A Computer-based Instrument	20
1.3	Structure of the Dissertation	25
2	BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORKS	28
2.1	Introduction	28
2.2	Sound Generation Models	29
2.2.1	Introduction	29
2.2.2	Abstract Models	29
2.2.3	Processed Recording	30
2.2.4	Spectral Models	30
2.2.5	Physical Models	31
2.2.6	Conclusions	31
2.3	Sound Description Models	32

CONTENTS	2
2.3.1 Introduction	32
2.3.2 Psychoacoustics	33
2.3.3 Signal Processing and MIR	38
2.3.4 Physical Models	39
2.3.5 Schaeffer's Typology	39
2.3.6 Conclusion	41
2.4 Mapping: from Description to Generation	41
2.4.1 Introduction	41
2.4.2 Mapping Categories	42
2.4.3 Mapping in Practice	43
2.4.4 Conclusion	44
2.5 Conclusion	45
3 CONTRIBUTIONS	46
3.1 Introduction	46
3.2 The Mapping Machine: an Introductory Overview	47
3.2.1 Architecture	47
3.2.2 Modularity	48
3.2.3 Workflow	48
3.3 Analysis/Synthesis Paradigm	52
3.3.1 Harmonic Additive Model	52
3.3.2 Principal Component Synthesis	56
3.4 Mapping Learning	61
3.4.1 An Introduction to Machine Learning	61

<i>CONTENTS</i>	3
3.4.2 Support Vector Machine	63
3.4.3 Support Vector Regression	64
3.5 Feature extraction	65
3.5.1 Controls/Inputs	66
3.5.2 Targets/ Outputs	73
3.6 Training and results	75
3.6.1 Database	75
3.6.2 Model selection	78
3.6.3 Evaluation	79
3.6.4 Results	80
3.7 Applications	83
3.7.1 Data-driven Synthesis	83
3.7.2 Interaction-based Synthesis for Sustained Excitation Instruments	83
3.7.3 Pitch-shifting/ Time-warping	84
3.7.4 Cross-synthesis	84
3.7.5 Scalable Synthesis	84
3.7.6 Continuous Control over Timbre	84
3.7.7 Other	85
3.8 Summary	85
4 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS	87
4.1 Contributions	87
4.2 Improvements	89
4.3 Interactive Computer Based Instruments and the Sensorimotor System .	91

CONTENTS	4
A INTERFACES FOR CONTROLLING SOUND GENERATION	95
B BASIC EXPERIMENTS IN TANGIBLE INTERFACE DESIGN	100
B.1 Structural Overview	101
B.2 The Project	101
B.3 Data acquisition on the AVR Microcontroller	103
B.4 Modules	104
B.4.1 Visual feedback	107
B.4.2 Auditory Feedback/Sound Synthesis	110
C LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	112
D PUBLICATIONS	114

List of Figures

1.1	Interdisciplinarity of computer music ([Moore 1990])	21
1.2	Computer-based Performance Framework	22
1.3	Gesture to Control Data	23
1.4	Raw Controllers Dimension Reduction	23
1.5	Interface Design: From Data to Perceptual Controllers	24
1.6	Mapping Sonic Percepts to Synthesis Parameters	25
1.7	Interdisciplinarity in this dissertation	27
2.1	Sound Synthesis Taxonomy by J.O. Smith	29
2.2	Critical Bands	35
2.3	Absolute Threshold of Hearing	36
2.4	Fletcher-Munson curves (from Wikipedia)	37
3.1	Traditional View Musician/Teacher/Instrument	47
3.2	Modularity with OSC	49
3.3	Flowchart: Training and Testing the System	50
3.4	Synthesis framework	53
3.5	SMS Analysis flowchart (from smstools wiki)	55
3.6	PCA Analysis/Synthesis	57

LIST OF FIGURES

3.7 Time-varying Partial Amplitudes from Matrix A. Each color represents a different partial or row of the matrix 58

3.8 Time-varying envelopes 59

3.9 PC bases 60

3.10 time-varying amplitudes in a 3D PC bases space 60

3.11 Estimation of the time-varying amplitudes 61

3.12 map the training data non linearly into a higher-dimensional feature space an construct a separating hyperplane with maximum margin. 65

3.13 High-level control extraction 66

3.14 Visualization of the time-varying partial amplitudes in a SDIF files with sdif-edit software 67

3.15 Spectrum Computation: 1) packing the windowed sound signal in a fft buffer, 2) magnitude spectrum and 3) phase spectrum (from [Serra 1998]) 68

3.16 Peak detection: 1) peaks in the magnitude spectrum 2) peaks in the phase spectrum (from [Serra 1998]) 69

3.17 Peak continuation. g are the guides and p the spectral peaks (from [Serra 1998]) 69

3.18 Clean Fundamental Frequency Estimation 71

3.19 Smooth Fundamental Frequency Estimation 71

3.20 three-dimensional input vector: pitch, loudness, brightness 73

3.21 Pareto chart of the number of PCs against percentage of variance expressed 74

3.22 Test set trajectory in the PC space 75

3.23 Reconstructed partial trajectories from the 3D PC space 76

3.24 Continuous Perceptual Controls: Fundamental Frequency, Loudness estimation and Brightness 77

3.25 Target and estimated first PC trajectory of the training set 81

LIST OF FIGURES

7

3.26 Target and estimated first PC trajectories of the test set 81

3.27 Target/estimate correlation on the test set 82

4.1 Computer-based Performance Framework 92

A.1 My tremolo effect GUI in Qt with OSC communication 97

A.2 The same tremolo effect GUI in PD 97

A.3 Three stages of learning (from Bill Verplank in [Ju and Wright 2005]) 99

B.1 Feedback (From M. Wright [Ju and Wright 2005]) 101

B.2 Connectivity (From M. Wright [Ju and Wright 2005]) 102

B.3 Sensor Chain [Ju and Wright 2005] 104

B.4 Sketch of the Physical Interface 105

B.5 The Tangible Interface Prototype 108

B.6 My GUI for displaying the values of the different sensors in real-time 109

B.7 Virtual 3D representation of the tangible control surface representing in real-time the pressure exerted on each FSR at the corner of the physical wooden square. Here we can see that 3 FSR out of 4 are measuring some significant pressure from the user. . . 109

B.8 My GUI for controlling the display of the 3D openGL virtual surface 110

Index

- Abstract, 12
- Acknowledgements, 15
- action, 91
- adaptative system, 22
- adaptive system, 20, 93
- additive, 12, 52
- Allure, 40
- amplitude, 57
- Applications, 83
- Atmel, 101
- auditory feedback, 20
- AVR, 101
- Background, 28
- Bibliography, 116
- brightness, 72
- classification, 62
- Computer-based instrument, 20
- concatenative, 44
- Conclusion, 87
- Contributions, 46, 87
- control theory, 19
- Cross-synthesis, 84
- Data-driven Synthesis, 83
- Database, 75
- dimensionality, 12
- enactive, 98
- Feature, 65
- feature, 23
- feedback, 93
- FFT, 66
- FM, 29

- FSR, 106, 107
- gestural, 48
- gesture, 20, 22
- graphical interface, 19, 23
- Graphical User Interface, 95
- harmonic, 52
- harmonics, 53
- high, 28, 29
- human computer interaction, 19
- ICA, 56
- Index, 8
- Interdisciplinarity, 19
- Interfaces for Sound Generation,
95
- interpolation, 54
- Introduction, 17
- IR, 106
- kernel trick, 64
- KPCA, 56
- learning, 62
- List of Abbreviations, 112
- List of Figures, 5
- loudness, 72
- low, 46
- machine learning, 19
- Mapping, 24, 42
- mapping, 12, 19, 28
- mass, 40
- matter, 40
- Max MSP, 18
- Max-MSP, 104
- MIDI, 17, 18, 95, 104
- MIR, 38
- Model, 78
- Modularity, 48
- Motivation, 17
- MPEG4, 85

MPEG7, 85

Music V, 17

My experiments in physical inter-
face design, 100

NNMF, 56

non-linear, 12, 64

OSC, 95, 106

partial, 52, 57

PCA, 56

perception, 91

perceptual, 18, 23, 29

physical interface, 19

Pitch shifting/Time warping, 84

Prologue, 16

Psychoacoustics, 33

psychoacoustics, 37

Publications, 114

Pure Data, 18

regression, 62

robotics, 93

SAOL, 18

Scalable Synthesis, 84

SDIF, 66, 104

Sensor, 106

Sensorimotor, 91

sensory-motor, 20, 91

shape, 40

SMS, 44, 55, 66

sound description, 12, 19, 28

sound generation, 12, 19, 28

Spectral Analysis, 66

STFT, 66

supervised, 62

SVM, 78

SVR, 74

Table of Contents, 1

tangible, 23

Timbre, 37

timbre, 37, 85

training, 49

Unsupervised, 62

VRML, 18

WIMP, 98

Abstract

This research report deals with the problem of mapping sonic percepts to sound generation, i.e. mapping high-level perceptually meaningful descriptors to sound synthesis parameters. We give an overview of different models that are used for sound description, sound generation and suggest a classification of the techniques that allow mappings from the descriptive to the generative domain. Based on our study of the state of the art, we describe our own novel system for intuitive control of an additive sound synthesis model. We in fact propose a general framework for the extraction, abstraction, reproduction and transformation of timbral characteristics of a sound analyzed from recordings. We give a detailed description of our analysis/synthesis paradigm which is well-suited for a machine learning approach to a non-linear mapping problem. We also suggest an elegant way to reduce the dimensionality of the synthesis parameter space, while preserving the auditory quality of the resynthesis. We finally give a complete and coherent framework to train, tune and evaluate our system in an automatic, consistent and reproducible fashion. The results are promising, and this type of architecture yields various original audio and musical applications.

About the Author

Sylvain Le Groux graduated with a double diploma in Mechanics and Electrical Engineering from ESME, Paris and a Master of Science in Signal Processing from King's College London. He also holds a DEA from ENST, Paris 6 University and IRCAM in Acoustics, Signal Processing, and Computer Science applied to Music. Additionally, he holds diplomas of solfege and flute from the National Conservatory of Nantes, took improvisation classes with Collectif Polysons, Francois Merville, Myra Melford, Fred Frith, and is following a postgraduate course in composition at IUA, UPF.

Since he entered the doctoral programme at Universitat Pompeu Fabra, he has been working on the AudioClas project (Eureka E! 2668) at MTG, UPF. He also collaborated with La Kitchen, a French company specialized in interactive multimedia and spent one year as a visiting scholar at the University of California at Berkeley.

“.....Hermes is the one who invented the nine-stringed lyre. What is a musical instrument, if not a table on which one can compose a thousand languages, and as many melodies and chants? Its invention opens the way for an infinite number of inventions. This is good philosophy in action, whose excellent goal is to invent the transcendental space, the conditions, for possible inventions of the future. The invention of possible inventions. This is a good image, followed by a good generalization, of what I was pointing out a little while ago: the conditional space and time for transporting messages back and forth. So, touch all the strings of this instrument and compose at leisure the possible ballads: this opens up a whole time.....”

–*Michel Serres* [Serres 1995].

Acknowledgements

Thanks to Xavier Serra for being my supervisor.

Thanks to David Wessel for transmitting his passion to me, for being at the source of many inspiring ideas and valuable comments, and for giving me a reason to persevere.

Thanks to Bill Verplank and Matt Wright for introducing me to the jolly world of physical interactive instrument design.

Thanks to the IIE, Lury Trust, and ANRT for their much needed financial support last year. I wish the list would be longer...

Thanks to my mother for her moral and, on certain occasions this year, extra financial support.

Thanks to my friends for being part of my life.

Thanks to Gert Lanckriet for providing me with a long-awaited cheap laptop. Now I have no excuse if a “concert-ready” implementation of my system is not available soon...

Thanks to the Myra Melford class, to the Ensemble Crumble, to Gabriel Brncic and to all the musicians I admire and listen to for allowing me not to forget music too much.

Thanks to Sergi Jorda and Perfecto Herrera for their useful comments.

Prologue

“...With the aid of electronic computers, the composer becomes a sort of pilot: he presses the buttons, introduce coordinates, and supervises the controls of a cosmic vessel sailing in the space of sound, across sonic constellations and galaxies that he could formerly glimpse only as a distant dream. Now he can explore them at his ease, seated in an armchair...”

–Iannis Xenakis, *Formalized Music*. [Xenakis 1971]

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

“We’ve got to undo the MIDI revolution !”

– *Miller Puckette.*

1.1 Motivation

Nowadays, personal computers are able to synthesize high quality sounds, and sound synthesis software has become largely accessible. Yet, the use of these tools can be quite intimidating and even counter intuitive for non-technically oriented users. Building new interesting synthesized sounds, and controlling them often requires a high level of technical expertise. One of the current challenges of sound and music computing is to find a way to control synthesis in a natural, intuitive manner. Most of the time the relation between a change of synthesis parameter (reified, for instance, as a knob in a graphical interface, or as a gesture captured from a sensor system) and its effect on our perception of the synthesized sound is not predictable. In our work, we intent to answer the following question: How can we provide the user with a musical, intuitive way to control sound synthesis?

A pioneer work in musical sound synthesis was the Music-n generation system, of which the most renowned example is Music-5 [Mathews 1969].

SAOL [Vercoe et al. 1998, Scheirer 1998], Max-MSP, Pure Data, [Puckette 1997, Zicarelli 1998, Puckette 1988] and most of the recent real-time software can be considered descendants of Music-n. These systems are built on the description of synthesis algorithms called patches, and are composed of interconnected modules that generate and transform signals. For example, an oscillator module generates a signal, and an envelope module applies an amplitude modulation to the signal to form a note. Generally, different patches (or types of synthesis) create different sound classes. Usually those sound synthesis methods rely on the same methodology: the user gives the synthesis algorithm and the synthesis parameters to the computer, and these produce a sound as an output.

The objective of this research is to build a system where the user (musician, sound designer, interactor) may give the synthesis system the desired acoustic properties (i.e. high-level, perceptually meaningful sound descriptors) instead of low-level technical synthesis parameters. The system will generate a sound with these desired properties by "intelligently" using the corresponding synthesis algorithms and parameters. This provides the user with more intuitive control, since the system processes the requests for her. The descriptors are high-level, and of a perceptual quality (In the case of additive synthesis, this report presents a system where the controllers are loudness, pitch, and timbral parameters, instead of sinusoidal frequencies and amplitudes). Our long-term goal is somewhat analog to VRML in the visual domain, where one can describe visual scenes with shape descriptors, position descriptors, texture descriptors, etc. Synthesis from high-level sonic percepts paves the way for a more detailed study of the coupling between perception and action in auditory and musical instrument interfaces, since the user is given direct control (action) over perceptual properties of the sound (perception).

Sound generation is a continuous timely process and many musical gestures are continuous. Nevertheless most of the tools commonly used for controlling sound synthesis (samplers, MIDI keyboards) are based on discrete event protocols. These models of control are relatively successful for instruments with low degree of interaction (piano for instance), but not

for sustained excitation instruments that need a continuous control over sound synthesis parameters. Our objective is to achieve fine continuous control over sound generation with a synthesis system based on auditory perception.

Our intention is to enrich the experience for both the musician and listener through the development of "expressive" technological tools.

1.2 Context

1.2.1 Interdisciplinarity

Our research project is interdisciplinary (Figure 1.1) by nature, and we have put a lot of efforts into acquiring as much expertise as possible in the different fields it connects to. Our proposition is to find a means to generate sounds from controls that are closely related to perception, and to implement the corresponding system. This specific research subject is related to various active fields of research. The sound generation component of the project involves extensive knowledge of **audio signal processing** techniques and **acoustical models** of instruments (Sections 2.2 and 3.3). The sound description component involves the understanding of the human **auditory system**, **psychoacoustics** and **information retrieval** issues (Sections 2.3 and 3.5). Moreover, the mapping from control to sound generation rely on **machine learning** techniques, a sub-branch of **artificial intelligence** (Section 3.4) and can be approached from a **control theory** ([Jordan and Rumelhart 1992]) perspective. All the different components of the system we describe here have also been modeled, implemented and tested as **computer programs**. In a "real life" situation, one uses **physical interfaces** or **graphical interfaces** to change the control parameter values. Therefore, the field of **human computer interaction** and **device design** has also a role to play in our project. In this report, we only describe some initial practical experiments in musical instrument design (Appendix B), as an illustration of

what can be done with relatively basic technological tools. In the future, we will develop more complex tangible interfaces specifically designed for our perceptually-controlled synthesizer paradigm.

A particularly interesting and rich approach to computer-based musical performance, is to view the musician and her instrument as an overall adaptive system [Lee and Wessel 1992] (cf Fig. 4.1). In the present report we focus our efforts on devising a model for **human interaction** with a sound synthesizer, where the interaction is based on perceptual controllers. We are not dealing with the sensory-motor system constituted by the human interactor itself, but instead the musician a perceptually meaningful interface to produce sounds (cf Fig. 4.1). Recent research in cognitive sciences and psychology emphasizes the importance of the study of **auditory feedback** in relation to musical actions (see [Pfordresher 2005]). In what way does music performance rely on the sounds that accompany musical gestures? Here, we present a system that directly maps percepts to sound generation. We describe how we implemented an additive synthesizer which is controlled by high-level sound descriptors such as loudness, pitch or other timbral attributes. This is an original analysis by synthesis technique, where what is usually defined as auditory feedback (perceptual properties of the sound) is used as a sound synthesis controller.

1.2.2 A Computer-based Instrument

Our aim is to help intuitive control of musical sound generation. In the framework we propose, the user gives the sound generation engine a high-level, perceptually meaningful timbre descriptor as control data, and the system maps those controls to the appropriate synthesis parameters.

The act of performing music is most probably guided by the auditory feedback one get as a consequence of a musical gesture or action. The coordination of perception and action in musical situation is a subject that

Figure 1.1: Interdisciplinarity of computer music ([Moore 1990])

Figure 1.2: Computer-based Performance Framework

is still not well understood or unified. In the following chapters, we are studying and proposing a model of the computer-based instrument, not the human interactor. Several studies have explored the optimization of the communication between human performers and sound producing units [Rovan et al. 1997, Wanderley and Depalle 1999, Ungvary and Vertegaal 2000]. Here, we describe a mechanism that allows to synthesize sounds from perceptually meaningful parameters. As can be seen on Fig. 4.1, influenced by [Lee and Wessel 1992], the sound generation engine based on perceptual controller is a subpart of the whole system that constitutes the musician/instrument adaptive system.

Hereafter we propose a decomposition of what we believe are the main building blocks of a modern digital music instrument, and indicate where the perceptual mapping (the main topic of this research) intervenes. Each output of one diagram is the input of the following diagram.

1. From gesture data to raw control data (Fig. 1.3): user's ges-

Figure 1.3: Gesture to Control Data

Figure 1.4: Raw Controllers Dimension Reduction

tures are captured via physical (tangible) or graphical interfaces, and interpreted by pattern recognition techniques (often based on machine learning algorithms). This leads to a set of raw continuous and discrete control data.

2. **From high-dimensional raw control data to low-dimensional control data** (Fig. 1.4): feature extraction techniques are applied to raw control data. We look for correlations between controls, and extract only the meaningful controls or gestures. It allows for a reduction of the number of relevant control parameters.
3. **Mapping low-dimensional control data to perceptual control**

Figure 1.5: Interface Design: From Data to Perceptual Controllers

(Fig. 1.5): this part is more a problem of subjective design choices. The user decides which controller would influence which perceptive quality of the sound. This is mostly done through a trial and error interaction design approach.

4. **Mapping perceptual control to low dimensional synthesis parameters** (Fig. 1.6): This is probably one of the most important and difficult part of the system. The synthesizer is trained (via machine learning techniques, for instance) to produce the sound corresponding to perceptual features. We want the musical intention of the user to be mapped onto the corresponding synthesis parameters. A priori, the synthesis parameter space is high-dimensional, but with common dimensionality reduction techniques (Principal Component Analysis for instance), we can reduce the number of relevant parameters, and the machine learning component only needs to map from a low dimensional control space to a relatively low dimensional parameter space.

As already stated above, this report mainly focuses on the inverse problem; namely, on the mapping from perceptual features, or musical in-

Figure 1.6: Mapping Sonic Percepts to Synthesis Parameters

tentions, to sound generation parameters. This problem is probably the most difficult and in our opinion the most fundamental one. The process of hearing in human involves perceptual representations thanks to the analysis system that constitutes the internal ear, and to its information abstraction system that constitutes the different integration stages in the brain. Therefore it seems important to take into account high-level, perceptually relevant controls in the mapping layer to be able to produce sounds in an intuitively satisfying manner.

1.3 Structure of the Dissertation

This research report is mainly divided into two complementary parts. The first part (Chapter 2 on page 28) aims at giving an overview of the current state of the art of the techniques and concepts related to our research project, while the second part (Chapter 3 on page 46) is a presentation of our own work.

In the first part, we introduce and classify the different synthesis algorithms that are commonly used to generate sounds with good quality (Section 2.2 on page 29). We also present and categorize different schemes that can be used to describe sounds in a meaningful way (Section 2.3 on page 32). Finally we give a survey of various approaches to

mapping high-level controls to sound synthesis parameters (Section 2.4 on page 41).

In the second part, after presenting the general architecture of our system (Section 3.2 on page 47), we describe the analysis/synthesis model we implemented (Section 3.3 on page 52), and introduce the statistical and machine learning techniques we applied (Section 3.4 on page 61). The next section 3.5 on page 65 is dedicated to the definition of the system's inputs and outputs, and the practical extraction of features for control and synthesis parameter estimation. In the section 3.6 on page 75, we explain how we train, tune, and evaluate the machine learning component of our model. Finally, in the section 3.7 on page 83 we present different applications that stem from the possibility of mapping intuitive sonic percepts to sound generation.

Figure 1.7 shows how the content of this dissertation relates to the various fields that constitutes computer music.

Figure 1.7: Interdisciplinarity in this dissertation

Chapter 2

BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORKS

“Being brilliant is no great feat if you respect nothing.”

– *Johann Wolfgang von Goethe.*

2.1 Introduction

In this chapter, we review the current techniques and knowledge in sound description, sound generation and the possible mappings existing between those two domains. We put the emphasis on the elements that are relevant to the context of the high-level control of sound synthesis algorithms: which sound description scheme could provide us with an interesting set of high-level controllers? Which sound generation model is suited to our needs? How can we control a sound generation model from a sound description model? We conclude each overview by a justification of our own design choices motivated by an analysis of the state of the art.

Processed Recording	Spectral Model	Physical Model	Abstract Algorithm
Concrète Wavetable T Sampling Vector Granular Prin. Comp. T Wavelet T	Wavetable F Additive Phase Vocoder PARSHL Sines+Noise (Serra) Prin. Comp. F Chant VOSIM Risset FM Brass Chowning FM Voice Subtractive LPC Inverse FFT Xenakis Line Clusters	Ruiz Strings Karplus-Strong Ext. Waveguide Modal Cordis-Anima Mosaic	VCO,VCA,VCF Some Music V Original FM Feedback FM Waveshaping Phase Distortion Karplus-Strong

Figure 2.1: Sound Synthesis Taxonomy by J.O. Smith

2.2 Sound Generation Models

2.2.1 Introduction

In the synthesis from high-level features, the corresponding synthesis algorithm is not given in advance. The goal of this dissertation is the construction of a synthesizer that accepts as an input a group of perceptually relevant descriptors.

Many different sound synthesis techniques have already been devised. They can be classified into four main categories, following Smith taxonomy [Smith 1991]: abstract algorithms, processed recordings, spectral models, and physical models.

2.2.2 Abstract Models

The first group of synthesis methods is called abstract algorithm models. They are usually simple and easy to implement. Nevertheless, they often sound artificial if compared to other more complex synthesis techniques. Abstract models includes synthesis schemes such as FM synthesis, particularly efficient for the synthesis of bell-like and metallic sounds,

wave-shaping (or non-linear distortion) synthesis, and Karplus strong algorithm typically used for the synthesis of plucked string or percussive sounds.

Abstract algorithms create interesting sounds but using techniques that are not related to the real world sound production mechanisms. They allow for the creation of new arbitrary sounds, and are computationally efficient for average quality synthesis of existing musical instruments.

2.2.3 Processed Recording

The second group is based on processed recordings. It includes simple sampling synthesis, consisting in the play-back of short recording of sounds, wave-table synthesis, which principle is to store typical portions of an instrument sound in tables to be able to loop them, play them back, and shift the pitch. Finally, granular synthesis idea is to represent the sound by elementary units or grains, which shape and temporal distribution change the synthesised sound.

Processed recording techniques allow for the reproduction of existing recorded sounds. It is also possible to merge, and morph between recorded sounds. Moreover, short grain of sounds, or recordings can be used to produce new sounds. Sampling techniques are particularly useful for applications demanding high-quality audio rendering.

2.2.4 Spectral Models

The spectral methods attempt to model the properties of sound accordingly to the perception of the listener. These synthesis techniques are more general, since any sound can be treated. Techniques based on the spectral model include additive synthesis, that models the signal by a sum of weighted sinusoids, the phase vocoder (that can be viewed either

as a bank of filters or as a short term Fourier transform analyzer), source-filter synthesis, Mc Aulay-Quatieri algorithm and Spectral Modeling Synthesis (SMS), that decompose any signal into a deterministic part and a stochastic part.

Spectral modeling uses information of the properties of the sound as it is perceived by the listener. This method is well suited for simulation and analysis of existing sounds and is adapted to good pitch-shifting time-scaling modifications.

2.2.5 Physical Models

Finally, physical models continue to develop as they allow a better control over the synthetic instrument parameters. This final group can itself be divided into five categories, namely a numerical solving of partial differential equations, source filter modelling, vibrating mass-spring network, modal synthesis and waveguide synthesis.

Physical models attempt to simulate the sound production mechanism of a real instrument. This model is useful for the simulation and analysis of physical instruments. Not only is it useful for studying the instrument physics but also for the creation of physically unrealizable instruments (by changing the range of the physical parameter values.) Application requiring control of high fidelity can take advantage of the fine physical control characteristics of physical models. One major problem with physical modeling is that for each instrument, one may need an entirely new model and algorithm to produce a realistic sound.

2.2.6 Conclusions

The synthesizer described in Chapter 3 of this dissertation uses an additive analysis/synthesis model. This model is chosen for its ability to

synthesize a large range of sounds while sounding quite natural (which unfortunately is sometimes not the case for abstract models).

Unlike physical models, the additive model is based on the original recorded sounds. It doesn't require having a theoretical representation of the physical property for each different instrument. Since the concept of additive synthesis is quite old and has been often used in electronic music, theoretical and practical tools for additive analysis are reliable and well documented. The concept of additive synthesis is quite simple; nevertheless, it can require many parameters to get a satisfactory sounding result. Besides, these parameters are not always adapted to a musical control of the synthesis.

By introducing both a principal component analysis for the reduction of parameters, and a machine learning algorithm for a flexible control of sound, this dissertation proposes a new and flexible scheme for musical control of sound. (C.f. Chapter 3).

In any case, it should be mentioned that the framework we devised in Chapter 3 for mapping from sound percepts to synthesis parameters is general enough so it can be applied, in principle, to any sound generation model.

2.3 Sound Description Models

2.3.1 Introduction

Sound synthesis software and techniques are largely accessible, but are still difficult to use for non-technically oriented users. Well-defined and general high-level control parameters are still missing.

A lot of work has been done to study and extract sound descriptors for classification, recognition and retrieval purposes. We aim at extending

those results to the domain of synthesis control. What kind of descriptors could be musically interesting controllers? What are the needs of a sound designer? Can we define a small semantic group that allows for the description of any kind of sounds?

In this section we will give an overview of different schemes that have been used to describe sounds. Sound descriptors can be high-level, such as those used in certain synthesis methods, developed in physical models, defined in psychoacoustics or extracted from signal processing techniques. Since our research is focused on the mapping of sonic percepts to synthesis parameters, we will put an emphasis on sound descriptors that are related to some perceptual reality, and could be used for high-level synthesis.

2.3.2 Psychoacoustics

There are five main components that constitutes our perception of sound. Namely the pitch, the loudness, the duration, the timbre, and the spatialization [Rasch and Plomp 1982]. Timbre is a multidimensional attribute of the sound defined by the negative as the perceptual attribute of sound that allows a listener to distinguish among sounds that are otherwise equivalent in pitch, loudness and subjective duration. Psychoacoustics is the discipline that describes the relationship between acoustic events and the resulting auditory perception. In the following section, we will give the definition of several fundamental psychoacoustical concepts.

2.3.2.1 Pitch

The pitch is at the same time related to the fundamental frequency of the audio signal (pitch height) and to its place in a musical scale (chroma). Pitch height vary directly with the frequency in the audible frequency range. Pitch chroma, on the contrary, models the perceptual phenomenon of octave equivalence that is to say the fact that two sounds at different

octave are perceived as sharing a common perceptual property. The limit of human audition are approximately from 20Hz to 20 kHz, but in a musical context, pitch perception is not accurate below 60Hz or above 5kHz ([Schubert 1979])

In fact, the perception of frequency also depends on frequency. Physiologically, auditory stimulus at certain frequency are associated with a specific loqui response along the ear's basilar membrane. Hearing works like a non-uniform filterbank, and the critical bands are a way to approximate this behavior.

Critical bands, introduced by Fletcher [Fletcher 1940] were firstly introduced when explaining the masking of a narrow band (sinusoidal) signal by a wideband (noise) source. It's a range of frequencies over which the masking Signal to Noise Ratio remains more or less constant.

$$BW(f) = 100Hz, \text{ if } f < 500Hz \text{ and } 0.2 * f \text{ if } f > 500Hz \quad (2.1)$$

Those bandwidths are used to form a critical band scale in Bark [Zwicker and Terhardt 1980]

$$z = 13 * \arctan(0.76f) + 3.5 * \arctan\left(\frac{f}{7.5}\right)^2 \quad (2.2)$$

where z is in Bark and f in kHz

The human auditory system analyzes broad band signals into critical bands, and the Bark scale representation is closer to our perception. However, pitch perception phenomenon is even more complex as pitch also depends on loudness and duration of notes.

2.3.2.2 Loudness

Loudness is a measure of the perceptual intensity of a sound. It is dependant on four main different variables, namely intensity, spectral content and time.

Fig. 4. Critical band measurement methods: (a) and (c) detection threshold decreases as masking tones transition from auditory filter passband into stopband, thus improving detection SNR, and (b) and (d) same interpretation with roles reversed (after [42]).

Figure 2.2: Critical Bands

A first rough approach to loudness would be to follow the Fechner law that states that a sensation (loudness) is proportional to the logarithm of the excitation (pressure level of the audio signal).

$$L_p = 20 \log_{10}(p/p_0) \tag{2.3}$$

where p_0 is the reference and p is the root-mean-square sound pressure being measured.

But once again, things are more complicated than it seems. It appears that the ear is more sensitive to certain frequencies than others. The absolute threshold of hearing curve demonstrates this sensitivity in frequency of the ear. It gives the amount of energy needed in a pure tone such that it can be detected by a listener in a noiseless environment. Experiments have shown that the absolute threshold of hearing varies with frequency of the test sound in the following fashion :

$$L_{dB} = 3.64f^{-0.8} - 6.5 \exp(-0.6(f - 3.3)^2) + 10^{-3}f^4 \tag{2.4}$$

Figure 2.3: Absolute Threshold of Hearing

Where L is in dB and f in kHz.

We can see that the transfer function in Figure 2.3 shows an attenuation in the lower and higher registers of the spectrum, and an emphasis around 2-5 kHz.

The Fletcher and Munson [Fletcher and Munson 1933] curves in Figure 2.4 exhibit equal-loudness contours as perceived by the human ear or phons.

Auditory perception is complex, and many other factors are to be taken into account to fully understand the way human perceive sounds (For instance, masking phenomena in the frequency and time domain, and other properties such as those exploited in the MPEG-1 Audio Layer 3 codecs, more commonly know as mp3 format). Nevertheless those first definitions are a good starting point and take into account the most important characteristics of the auditory system.

Figure 2.4: Fletcher-Munson curves (from Wikipedia)

2.3.2.3 Timbre

A first approach to defining a group of sound descriptors comes from psychoacoustics studies of timbre.

The psychoacoustics approach for the study of timbre is generally to describe perceptual dimensions of sounds from abstract descriptors. Those acoustic descriptors can be spectral, temporal or spectro-temporal, and generate a “timbre space” [McAdams et al. 1995, Grey 1975, Wessel 1979].

The timbre space is determined using multidimensional analysis on data taken from experiments where a listener has to judge of the dis/similarity of pairs of sounds. Those pair of sounds differ only by their timbral characteristics. Multidimensional analysis techniques allow to extract a set of “principal axes” which try to explain well the answer of the listeners. Once the principal axes have been found, we try to find acoustical descriptors that correlate with those axes derived from multidimensional

analysis.

The most common descriptors that are unveiled by psychoacoustics studies realized on different musical instrument's sounds are the centroid, the spectral spread [Peeters et al. 2000], the log-attack time and the spectral flux.

2.3.3 Signal Processing and MIR

The problem of sound description is also addressed by the Music Information Retrieval (MIR) community, driven by a strong industrial need. A particularly interesting goal for the music industry is to find relevant sound descriptors for helping retrieval and classification of specific audio files (songs, sound effects, ...) in large databases.

Usually, a large set of descriptors from various fields (psychoacoustics but also speech processing, signal processing, ...) is computed. We can distinguish between several feature's characteristics: the **steadiness/dynamics** of the feature; the **time extent** of the description provided by the feature; and the **globalness** or **instantaneousness** of the feature, depending on whether it's computed on each frame or on the whole signal [Peeters 2003], [Vinet et al. 2002]. Those features are usually numerous (order 50) [AudioClas] and describe various aspect of an audio signal such as the temporal shape, the spectral shape, the harmonic content, and some perceptual parameters. For MIR applications, Statistics (mean, variance, etc.) on these features are usually used to calculate distances between sounds or groups of sounds. Some particularly relevant descriptor for timbre are spectral centroid and spectral spread, studied in psychoacoustics but also spectral skewness and kurtosis.

Some other features are perceptually relevant, and can lead to interesting control of sound by reverse engineering. For instance, the fundamental frequency of a harmonic sound can be assimilated to pitch, the spectral centroid is correlated to brightness [McAdams et al. 1995].

Some descriptors such as roughness, signal to noise ratio, formant position, vibrato are at the limit between signal parameters and psycho-acoustical parameters, but are relevant in characterizing a sound source [Arfib et al. 2002].

2.3.4 Physical Models

A third approach to defining the group of descriptors is inspired by physical models of instruments. Simplified physical models of different kinds of instrument (clarinet, trumpet, violin, flute, etc.) already exist. The sounds produced by these dynamic systems are very similar to the corresponding instruments. It is possible to deduce a relation between the characteristic timbres and the properties of the produced signals.

Here some perceptual characteristics are directly related to the physical parameters of the mode (volume of the object, material, elasticity...) [McAdams and Bigand 1993]. Other important factors come from the resonating properties of instruments, as well as from different ways of exciting the instrument (hitting it, bowing it, breathing into it, etc.). Control parameters of physical models are at the same time low-level because they are related to a mathematical model, and high-level in the sense that they are strongly correlated to a perceptual physical reality [Arfib et al. 2002].

2.3.5 Schaeffer's Typology

Schaeffer's taxonomy or "solfege of musical objects" [Schaeffer 1966] is an intuitive and useful tool for the description of synthesized or natural sounds, and is virtually applicable to any class of sound. His taxonomy is based on the pair shape/matter. The matter criteria correspond to what we would hear if we could freeze the sound, while the shape is related to the variation of matter in time.

Within the **matter criteria** category, the **mass** is related to the perception of pitchness of a sound (and indeed its spectral distribution). For classification, this criterion can be further divided into three distinct subclasses, namely noisy (unpitched), pitched (single pitch), complex (noise and pitch or multiple pitch).

Harmonic Timbre is a finer characterization of the mass associated with brightness (or spectral centroid).

Finally, a **grain** is related to the microstructure of the sound. Again it can be subdivided in subtypes: resonant, for non sustained sounds (like a cymbal), rubbing for sustained sounds (bow, breath), and iterative grain (drum roll).

Within the **shape criteria** category, **dynamics** defines the evolution of intensity or amplitude envelope (We can associate this criterion to evolution of loudness). For further classification purposes, several classes such as varying, varying-impulse, varying iterative (several transients), varying-delta, varying-crescendo, varying-decrescendo or other can be defined. **Allure** is related to Amplitude or frequency modulation.

We now come to the definition of the components of the **variation criteria**. The **melodic profile** is the type of pitch variation (for pitched sounds) or frequency-range variation (for noisy sounds). Unvarying, varying-continuous (siren), varying-stepped (piano), and varying chaotic are possible subclassification of this criterion.

The **mass profile** is the type of mass variation, i.e. varying from noisy to pitched or unvarying.

This taxonomy appears to be general enough to be able to describe almost any natural or synthetic sound. Some of its members are correlated to those of other descriptor schemes (harmonic timbre and centroid, allure and amplitude or frequency modulation, mass and pitchiness). This kind of description is mainly thought as describing patterns in sounds though. It's original goal was to create a taxonomy for classification at a

higher musical level than sound texture description itself. Most of those descriptors could be useful to choose between presets (discrete) of general sound synthesis parameters, but not for continuous control of timbre synthesis in a real-time situation. They are nevertheless useful in the sense that they allow to describe sounds generally without having to rely on excessively technical terms.

2.3.6 Conclusion

We gave an overview of various approaches to describing sounds. We put the emphasis on the characteristics of each approach and showed the relevance of some descriptors that can be used for high-level synthesis because of their correlation with perceptive attributes. Various studies [Gaver 1993, Vanderveer 1979, Mynatt 1994] have shown that listeners prefer to describe sounds at the perceptual level rather than the signal level. This legitimates the building of a sound synthesis systems that is controlled at this perceptual level. We studied a set of perceptually relevant controllers and we want a system that maps the perceptual level (characteristics of the sound) to the signal level (how the sound can be synthesized).

2.4 Mapping: from Description to Generation

2.4.1 Introduction

In the previous sections, we presented a review of the state of the art for sound generation and sound description models. Our final objective is to be able to intuitively generate sounds from a set of perceptual high-level descriptors. In the following section we will make the distinction between different categories of mapping, and present the mapping techniques or

solution that have been explored to bridge the gap between the perceptual controls and the parameters of a sound generation model. Here our interest is in a perceptual mapping seen as an improvement over simpler two layer mappings [Arfib et al. 2002, Wanderley et al. 1998].

2.4.2 Mapping Categories

We can distinguish different types of mappings from control parameters to sound synthesis parameters [Arfib et al. 2002].

A first distinction [Hunt et al. 2000] is the difference between **explicit** and **implicit** mapping. Explicit mapping implies that the relationship between the controls and the synthesis parameters is directly expressible by means of a mathematical expression. Implicit mapping suggests that the mapping is done “automatically”. We give the mapping component of the system some rules, some knowledge about a general behavior, about the data, but not the exact mapping function. A typical example of this kind of mapping is a machine learning “black-box model” such as neural network regression. We train a network to learn a relationship between its input (control) and outputs (synthesis) parameters by minimizing an error between the predicted value and the original parameters. The neural network learns the appropriate mapping function from data.

Another distinction is the difference between **dynamic** and **static** mapping. Here two different interpretation of the concepts are possible [Arfib et al. 2002]. Firstly, a dynamic mapping can be defined as a mapping that will be able to evolve, change in time, and adapt to the changes in data. On the other hand, dynamic mapping can also refer to a mapping from dynamic description of control parameters to synthesis parameters (An example of this kind of mapping can be found in [Momeni and Henry 2006]).

Finally, complexity gives yet another distinctive characteristic of a mapping technique. One can distinguish between **complex** mappings and **simple** mappings. Complex mappings are defined as a mapping from

many control parameters to many synthesis parameters [Hunt et al. 2000]. On the contrary, simple mappings are straightforward one-to-one relationships between one control parameter and one sound generation parameters.s

2.4.3 Mapping in Practice

Various prior works are related to this research and provided different complementary views and ways to frame the problem of mapping high-level controls to synthesis. A few studies have explored the control of audio synthesis from perceptual parameters. We can distinguish three main trends: the machine learning view, where a model of the timbre is learned from audio data, the concatenative view, where the timbre is “constructed” by the juxtaposition of pre-existing sonic grains, and the signal processing view, where the transformations on timbre are model-dependant and direct applications of the signal model affordances.

The first representant of the machine learning point of view is found in [Lee and Wessel 1992] where a detailed description of a connectionist model for real time control of synthesis is articulated by the authors. They present the problem of transformation of performance gestures into control parameters. A general forward-model was analyzed, and the importance of both the pre-processing of gestural data as well as the perceptually based representation of sounds was underscored. Later on, [Wessel et al. 1998] applying the ideas presented in the initial study [Lee and Wessel 1992] compared a neural network model with a memory based machine learning technique. The network described in this second study received fundamental frequency and loudness in its input layer, and was trained to estimate amplitudes and frequencies of the sound partials. Additional Research on the modelling of speech and music signal was presented in [Robel 1997]. While the Radial Basis Function neural network employed in this third study was particularly adapted for the prediction of time series, the system described lacked variety in choice of controllers. In another study, [Jehan and Schoner 2001] the authors borrowed the

general ideas presented in [Wessel et al. 1998] but replaced the artificial neural network component with the Cluster Weighted Model devised by Schoner [Jehan and Schoner 2001], and added a model of noise analysis/synthesis. The Cluster Weighted Model technique is equivalent to a hierarchical mixture of expert model proposed in [Jordan and Jacobs 1994].

In the case of concatenative synthesis [Schwartz 2004], a sound is defined as a combination of pre-existing samples in a database. These samples (or units) are already analyzed, classified in the database and can be retrieved by their audio characteristics. Concatenative synthesis can synthesize well transitions in an instrument, and high-level control of synthesis is allowed by selecting units that correspond to a desired value of a sound attribute. For a good introduction to concatenative synthesis, as well as an historical review and taxonomy, the reader is reported to [Schwarz 2005].

Finally, in [Serra and Bonada 1998], the authors propose a set of timbral transformations based on the SMS model [Serra 1998]. High-level control of synthesis in this case is highly dependent on the possibility of the sound generation model. Since spectral models like SMS use information of the properties of the sound as it is perceived by the listener, it allows for transformation such as translation and distortion of the harmonic spectrum, or even higher-level control such as vibrato, tremolo and gender transformation of a voice.

2.4.4 Conclusion

Our approach to mapping is influenced by the machine learning view and the literature on control theory [Jordan and Rumelhart 1992]. It seems to be more general, a priori model-independent, and potentially more powerful. We advocate for a perceptual mapping process, as a means to build better interface suited to human sensitivity. This report documents our attempt to provide a general, coherent, automated, and reproducible mapping system that is general enough so it can be used in many different synthesis contexts.

2.5 Conclusion

In conclusion, after a careful overview of the different sound generation models, we saw that the most interesting models for our type of application were the additive analysis/synthesis model, and the physical models. In this dissertation we decided to start by studying high-level mappings to an additive analysis/synthesis model, because of its ability to generate many different sounds naturally. Nevertheless the mapping scheme proposed in this dissertation is general enough so it can be applied to other types of sound generation models.

In a second time, we gave an overview of various approaches to describing sounds. Listeners usually prefer to describe sounds at the perceptual level rather than the signal level. This fact legitimates our idea of building of a sound synthesis systems that is controlled at the perceptual level. We put the emphasis on the characteristics of each approach and showed the relevance of some descriptors that can be used for high-level synthesis because of their correlation with perceptive attributes.

Finally, we presented the state of the art in mapping high-level controllers to sound synthesis parameters. Our own approach to mapping is influenced by the machine learning view and the literature on control theory, because of its generality, powerfulness and independence towards sound synthesis models.

In the rest of the dissertation we tackle the problem of mapping sonic percepts to sound generating algorithms. We base our work on the conclusions we draw from Chapter 2 and we propose a coherent, automated, and reproducible mapping system that is general enough so it can be used in many different synthesis contexts.

Chapter 3

CONTRIBUTIONS

3.1 Introduction

In this chapter we present our personal views and propose preliminary solutions to the problem of mapping sonic perceptual controls to sound generation parameters. We first describe the general framework of our synthesizer system and precise some of its characteristics: its architecture, its modularity and the different tasks that have to be accomplished. In a second section (Section 3.3 on page 52) we explain in detail the specific analysis/synthesis paradigm we devised to represent a sound in a low-dimensional parameter space. In section 3.4 on page 61 we briefly present a few fundamental concepts in machine learning and give an introduction to the support vector regression algorithm we utilize to accomplish the mapping from controls to targets. Section 3.6 is dedicated to the details of the extraction of the features we want to use as controls and targets. Finally, section 3.6 gives a the practical and detailed explanation of the characterization of the database, the training procedure, and the evaluation process.

Figure 3.1: Traditional View Musician/Teacher/Instrument

3.2 The Mapping Machine: an Introductory Overview

3.2.1 Architecture

The structure of our system is straightforward and inspired by the “natural system” formed by a musician and his/her instrument. If we think in terms of traditional musical instruments, the controllers used by the musician to interact with the system are located on one side, and the sound synthesis engine, which plays the role of the instrument, is located on the opposite side. The machine learning component task is to transmit information and coordinate proper communication between these two elements. By analogy, its function is similar to that of a music teacher showing her students how to produce a correct sound out of their instrument’s body (synthesis engine), from a given finger position (controllers) (Fig. 3.1).

However, there is a limit (or extension depending on the point of view) to this music student/teacher analogy. Once the machine has learned, the system has acquired a kind of intelligence. Any control information, provided it is rescaled in the range of the training data, will produce a reliable sound. This allows for experiments with any kind of controllers.

This enhanced instrument adapts to the musician's control. For instance, it becomes possible to play the saxophone with flute control parameters and vice versa (see some applications in Chapter ?? on page ??). The relationship between the musician and her instrument is fundamentally changed. In our view, the machine learning component is itself an integral part of the instrument, as seen on figure 1.6 on page 25. While the musician traditionally has had to adapt to the physical properties of her instrument, the system described in this dissertation gives the musician extended freedom of choice in gestural control of the instrument.

3.2.2 Modularity

Another important characteristic differentiating this system from acoustic instruments is that the controllers and the synthesis engine are two distinct part of the system. The synthesis engine, consisting of the machine learning component and the sound synthesis algorithms, may be physically separated from the control information. This distinctness makes this kind of synthesis suited to client server applications, for instance. A user/interactor, via the controllers, plays the role of the client, and the synthesis engine that of the server. To give an example, a musician could remotely control this new instrument via Ethernet using the OSC protocol [Wright et al. 2003] (cf Fig. 3.2).

3.2.3 Workflow

Another important aspect of our model, in addition to its specific structure, is the timing of the different processes taking place. Since the machine learning algorithm must first be trained before any attempt to use the system, it is necessary to carefully describe the sequence of the different processes (Fig. 3.3). Each step of the setup required for the system to give proper results is described in the following sections.

Figure 3.2: Modularity with OSC

3.2.3.1 Choice of the training data set

First, the audio samples are chosen to fit the needs of the user. These samples should be as varied as possible and include the kinds of sonorities with which the user wishes to play. To give an example, an accurate simulation of all the acoustical properties of an instrument requires a large number of training samples. These samples should be able to describe the main possibilities of interpretation, transition and playing modes of the specific instrument. The choice of the training data set is fundamental, since it will determine the overall results, the “colour” of the sound synthesis and finally, the musical result.

3.2.3.2 Analysis

Once the choice of the training data is done, the audio samples are passed through an additive harmonic analysis tool. This step allows modelling

Figure 3.3: Flowchart: Training and Testing the System

the sound with a set of parameters that will later be modified depending on the control information. Here we use SMSTools, an open-source sound analysis software distributed by the MTG at Pompeu Fabra University [SMSTools]. The details of the parametrization we used are given in section 3.5.

3.2.3.3 Extraction of the control information

The results from this analysis are used for the extraction and definition of the perceptual controllers (such as pitch, loudness, brightness, ...). These controllers are the only connection between the user and the “instrument” and should be as convenient as possible from a musical and perceptual point of view.

3.2.3.4 Training of the Machine Learning Algorithm

Finally, the third step involves the training of the machine learning algorithm. The perceptual controllers information is sent as an input to the system (Fig. 3.3). The algorithm is then trained to map these controls to the set of the output parameters (targets) needed for driving the sound synthesis algorithm. The quality of the sound produced by the system is highly dependant on the training performances. Once the training is considered satisfactory, the system is ready for use. The parameters needed for the sound synthesis are estimated by the system, and the user can play with it.

We have presented and explained the overall structure and procedures constituting our system. The different parts of the system will be accurately defined in the following sections.

3.3 Analysis/Synthesis Paradigm

We chose the additive synthesis model for its ability to synthesize a large range of sounds. Unlike physical models, it is based on original recorded sounds. It doesn't require having a theoretical representation of the physical properties of each different instrument and it allows for a refined control over sound manipulation: the frequency, amplitude and phase of every partial can be controlled independently. Nevertheless, to obtain satisfactory results, additive models require controlling many synthesis parameters, which are not always intuitive or related to musical meaning.

First, we will introduce briefly the additive model. The problem of the high dimensionality of parameters is tackled in subsection 3.3.2, where we will show how to reduce the dimension of the parameter space in order to achieve additive synthesis from a low-dimensional space. The second problem of relating musically meaningful parameters to synthesis parameters is taken care of in the sections 3.6 and 3.4 on page 61. where we develop a method used for non-linear mapping from percepts to synthesis parameters based on support vector regression.

3.3.1 Harmonic Additive Model

The sound is represented as a sum of weighted sinusoids at frequencies multiple of the fundamental frequency. This model presupposes the sound is quasi harmonic and the frequencies, amplitudes and phases are varying slowly; nevertheless, the results obtained with this type of analysis prove satisfactory for our research objectives.

A quasi-periodic tone can be decomposed in a sum of sine waves with time-varying amplitudes and frequencies as such [Aulay and Quatieri 1986]:

$$y(n) \simeq \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} a_k(n) \sin(2\pi f_k(n) + \phi_k) \quad (3.1)$$

Figure 3.4: Synthesis framework

where n is the time index, N is the number of harmonics in the synthetic signal, $a_k(n)$ is the time-varying amplitude of the k th partial, $f_k(n)$ is the time-varying frequency of the k th partial, and ϕ_k is the corresponding phase. with $f_k = k \cdot f_0$ where f_0 is the fundamental frequency (harmonicity hypothesis) and $a_k(t)$ and $f_k(t)$ are slowly varying.

For the res-synthesis, the phase information, which is not perceptually relevant, is discarded. We discuss this choice in the following paragraph. We assume the sample $y(n)$ can be reconstructed from the fundamental frequency estimation vector \mathbf{f}_j (dimension number of frames) and the matrix of partial amplitudes $\mathbf{A}_{i,j}$ (dimension number of harmonics by number of frames).

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_{1,1} & \dots & a_{1,M} \\ \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ a_{N,1} & \dots & a_{N,M} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.2)$$

where N is the number of partials, and M is the number of analysis frames.

For the resynthesis, the samples $y(n)$ are reconstituted at the proper

sample rate F_s by linear interpolation between each frame of the analysis matrix $\mathbf{A}_{i,j}$ to give the coefficients $a_k(n)$. The procedure is similar for obtaining the coefficients $f_k(n)$. The analysis hop size gives the number of samples represented by each column of the matrix: $hop = \text{round}(F_s \cdot \text{frameDuration})$ where F_s is the sample rate in Hertz and frameDuration is in seconds.

The interpolation scheme allows the calculation of the time-varying coefficients between each frame:

$$a_k^j(n) = \frac{(a_{k,j+1} - a_{k,j})}{hop} \cdot n + a_{k,j} \quad (3.3)$$

where $a_k^j(n)$ is the time-varying amplitude of the partial k between the frame j and $j + 1$, a_k is the element of matrix \mathbf{A} corresponding to the partial k and to the frame j .

The same procedure is repeated for the interpolation of the fundamental frequency values between each frame and the synthesized sound is computed from equation 3.1. The analysis information provides a reliable abstract representation of the original audio signal.

We previously assumed that the influence of the phase was not primordial for resynthesis purposes. This assumption deserves an explanation. The phase for each partial (or each sinusoidal oscillator) can be observed as a difference in initial amplitude and direction. We based our decision to neglect the effects of the phase on an article by [Risset and Wessel 1982], where the authors discuss Ohm's acoustic law and state that "if the Fourier representations of two sounds have the same pattern of harmonic amplitudes but have different patterns of phase relationships, a listener will be unable to perceive a difference between the two sounds, even though the two sounds may have very different waveforms." Notice that this insensitivity to phase is only true for periodic tones, and doesn't hold anymore in a dispersive medium environments where frequencies propagate at different speeds. Nevertheless, for audible sounds, air can be considered as a non-dispersive medium (it is not true anymore for ultrasonic frequencies superior to 30kHz).

Figure 3.5: SMS Analysis flowchart (from smstools wiki)

We based our sound analysis on the SMS model which we won't detail here since it has been extensively studied and presented elsewhere. We report the reader to [Serra 1998] for a comprehensive explanation of the spectral analysis/synthesis paradigm, and for the exact methods employed to extract the frequencies, amplitude and phase parameters of the additive model we previously introduced. The main steps of the analysis process are summarized in Figure 3.5. Because we chose to use a simplified additive model for resynthesis as a first approach, we just need the sine magnitude and phase parameters. The practical choice of the analysis parameters such as the size of the short-term Fourier transform, the hop-size, the smoothing windows, etc are given in section 3.5. At this stage, we have obtained a parametrization of a sound represented by the matrix of time-varying amplitudes, and a matrix of the time-varying partial frequencies inferred from the time-varying fundamental frequency. Typically, this parametrization is of high dimension (hundreds of partials). In the next section we will explain how we managed to do synthesis from a reduced set of parameters while preserving the original quality of the synthesis.

3.3.2 Principal Component Synthesis

We want to reduce the dimensionality of the synthesis parameter space by finding a compact representation of the time-varying amplitude matrix, while being able to approximate well the original space from its low-dimensional representation. For this purpose, we use the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) technique [Jackson 1991, Shlens 2005]. PCA is one of the most commonly used techniques in modern data analysis. The goal of PCA is to compute the most meaningful basis to re-express a noisy data set.

Some other more advanced techniques such as Independent Component Analysis (ICA), Kernel PCA (KPCA), and since in our case the amplitude matrix is non-negative, Non-Negative Matrix Factorization (NNMF) and Non-Negative Independent Component Analysis (NNICA) could also be used to compute basis vectors for low-dimensional models of the amplitude matrix. The detailed study of their respective merits and efficiency for sound synthesis is a subject we propose to investigate in future works. The two non-negative techniques turn out to be especially interesting because the pseudo-inverse of their basis vectors is also close to being non-negative. Truncating the negative values usually incurs only a very slight performance penalty in terms of the accuracy with which the input spectrum can be approximated using a low-dimensional model.

In this report, we decided to focus on the PCA technique applied to the reduction of the dimension of the amplitude matrix. PCA is easy to compute, and has proved to be a powerful tool for many applications (Computer vision, Bio-informatics, Statistics, ...). In the context of musical timbre research, several studies have used PCA to analyze physical parameters of sound, searching for relationships to perceptive characteristics [Charbonneau et al. 1997b, Charbonneau et al. 1997a]. This is the traditional timbre space approach described earlier in Section 2.3.2.3. In this work, we use PCA as a data reduction tool for additive analysis parameters. The perceptual validity of this approach has been extensively studied in [Sandell and Martens 1995] in the case of phase vocoder pa-

Figure 3.6: PCA Analysis/Synthesis

rameters. Similarly, we obtained perceptually satisfying results (Section 3.5).

In this section, we propose a method to synthesize a quasi-harmonic sound from the low-dimensional principal component decomposition of the harmonic amplitude matrix (Fig. 3.6). Later, we will study how to relate this low-dimensional representation of synthesis data to perceptually meaningful descriptors (Section 3.4).

From a statistical analysis point of view, one row of the partial amplitude matrix $A_{i,j}$ (Fig. 3.7 shows the first 50 partials of a solo saxophone analysis file) is a variable (a particular partial amplitude trajectory), and one column is a measurement (a particular spectrum) for the j -th analysis frame.

First, we subtract the mean in each dimension (amplitude trajectory) and then, the covariance matrix of the partial amplitude matrix is calculated as such:

$$C_A = \frac{1}{n-1} \mathbf{A} \mathbf{A}^T \quad (3.4)$$

The ij^{th} element of C_A is the dot product between the i^{th} and j^{th} partial amplitude trajectories. C_A is a square symmetric matrix, which diagonal terms are the variance of the amplitude partials and the off-diagonal terms are their covariances.

This correlation matrix captures the correlations between all possible pairs, and reflects the noise (small diagonal values) and redundancy (large

Figure 3.7: Time-varying Partial Amplitudes from Matrix A . Each color represents a different partial or row of the matrix

off-diagonal values) in the additive analysis. The purpose of this principal component analysis is to reduce the redundancy (off-diagonal) that might be encountered in the additive analysis parameter space, and maximize the variance (diagonal). In other words, it comes down to diagonalizing C_A .

C_A is square, and symmetric and an eigenvector decomposition is performed in order to find an orthonormal basis of eigenvectors. The eigenvectors of the covariance matrix associated with the largest eigen-values lie in the direction of the largest data variance. We choose a small set of eigen (“feature”) vectors with the largest eigenvalues so that only the smallest amount of information is lost in the mean-square sense. They form the matrix F of dimension number of partials by number of eigenvector retained, or Principal Components (PC).

The data in the new bases is easily computed, by a projection of the original data on the principal components (eigen-vectors):

$$\mathbf{D} = \mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{A} \quad (3.5)$$

Figure 3.8: Time-varying envelopes

where D is the new data matrix (dimension number of principal components by number of frames). F is the feature matrix of eigen-vectors (dimension number of partials by number of principal components) and A_{ij} is the partial amplitude matrix as defined in Equation 3.2 (dimension number of partials by number of frames).

The time-varying envelopes D_i (for instance in Fig. 3.8 we are in dimension three) are trajectories in the new Principal Component (PC) basis F (Fig. 3.9 and 3.10). The new PC bases represent “principal spectra”, and a time-varying partial amplitude is a time-varying linear combination of those basis spectra.

It is possible to get an approximation of the original matrix from the low dimensional principal component space by multiplication of the PC bases matrix and the time-varying envelope matrix (Fig. 3.11 shows the first six estimations of amplitude partials, but we can compute all the estimates

Figure 3.9: PC bases

Figure 3.10: time-varying amplitudes in a 3D PC bases space

Figure 3.11: Estimation of the time-varying amplitudes

from the principal component space).

$$\hat{\mathbf{A}} \approx \mathbf{F}\mathbf{D} \quad (3.6)$$

We are now able to synthesize a sound from a reduced set of time-varying PC parameters. The next step is to map perceptual controls to those PC controls. This step is taken care of by the support vector machine learning algorithm, which we will briefly explain in the following section.

3.4 Mapping Learning

3.4.1 An Introduction to Machine Learning

Machine Learning evolved from the field of Artificial Intelligence which aims to reproduce intelligent human behaviors in machines. The Ma-

chine Learning field studies the possibilities of making machines able to learn. Learning here is understood as inductive inference, or the capacity to predict based on observations. Learning implies a lot of different processes but basically consists in gaining knowledge, or understanding by experience. It can thus be said that a machine has learned when it changes its program, its data, or its structure, based on the inputs it receive, and in such a way that the future performance is expected to improve. There are two main kind of learning. **Unsupervised learning** tries to uncover hidden regularities such as clusters or to detect anomalies in the data. In **supervised learning**, we know in advance the label, or target values, of a set of examples we train the machine on. When the target is discrete, the task is a **classification** problem. If the target is real-valued, the task is a **regression** problem.

One might wonder why we would use a machine that learns, instead of directly designing a machine that executes the task we want. If the study of human cognition is an argument in favour of exploring machine learning models, there are also some important engineering tasks that require this type of model [Nilsson 1999]. For instance, some tasks cannot be defined well except by example. Some important relationships or correlation information might be hidden in the data and extracted by machine learning. Some applications need on-the-job improvements of what is already existing. Finally, one might need an application that adapts to time-varying environments.

In our research, we want to be able to map continuous perceptual controllers to sound synthesis parameters. This mapping is based on the analysis of a recorded sound and its descriptors. We can have access to both the input and the desired target for a training set, thus a good way to define our task is by example. We can specify the input/output pairs (perceptual controls/synthesis parameters) from the audio analysis, but not a precise relationship between inputs and desired outputs. In consequence, supervised machine learning algorithms are well-suited to the kind of task we wish to tackle.

A mapping function associates an input vector to an output vector. Our

problem is to learn this function f . The hypothesis about the function is denoted h . f and h are functions of a real-valued input $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_i, \dots, x_n)$ with n components. The function h is selected based on a training set of input vector examples S . For supervised learning, we assume that if we can find a h that closely agree with f on the training data set, then this hypothesis h will be a good guess for f when the dataset is large enough.

3.4.2 Support Vector Machine

Support Vector Machines (SVMs) and kernel methods have become increasingly popular tools for such different tasks as data mining, classification, regression, and applications ranging from machine vision, handwritten digit recognition, to interpretation of gene expression data in bioinformatics.

We chose to apply this technique to the perceptual mapping problem based on good results the SVM algorithms obtained in various surveys from the machine learning community [Bennett and Campbel 2000], and on the improvement it could bring to previous related works. Compared to other approaches (for instance Artificial Neural Networks [Wessel et al. 1998] or Cluster-Weighted Modelling [Schoner 2000] were used for perceptual mapping), SVMs exhibit a lot of interesting properties. SVMs allies geometric intuition with elegant mathematics, and above all eliminates many of the problems experienced with other methodologies such as neural networks or decision trees. Namely, there are no more problems with local minima. We can build highly non-linear regression function without getting stuck in a local minima. Moreover, there's only a few model parameters to pick, and the final results are stable and reproducible unlike neural networks models where the result depends on the initial starting point. Finally, SVMs have been proven to be robust to noise in many applications [Bennett and Campbel 2000].

3.4.3 Support Vector Regression

Support vector machines (SVMs) [Scholkopf and Smola 2002] are a set of related supervised learning methods used for classification and regression. They use a technique known as "kernel trick" to apply linear techniques to non-linear problems.

The ε -SVR algorithm is a generalization of the better known Support Vector for Classification algorithm. For regression, the goal is to estimate an unknown continuous-valued function based on a finite set of training samples [Smola and Scholkopf 1998]. Given n training vectors \mathbf{x}_i and a vector y : (\mathbf{x}_i, y_i) , ($i = 1, \dots, n$) where $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and $y \in \mathbb{R}$, we optimally estimate the function $y = f(\mathbf{x})$, in the Structural Risk Minimization sense, by:

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^l (\alpha_i^* - \alpha_i) k(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}) + b \quad (3.7)$$

where b is a bias, $k(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x})$ is the kernel function and α_i^*, α_i the solution of the quadratic problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Maximize} \quad & \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=1}^l (\alpha_i^* - \alpha_i)(\alpha_j^* - \alpha_j) k(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j) \\ -\varepsilon \sum_{i=1}^l (\alpha_i^* + \alpha_i) + \sum_{i=1}^l (\alpha_i - \alpha_i^*) \end{cases} \\ \text{Subject to} \quad & \begin{cases} \sum_{i=1}^l (\alpha_i - \alpha_i^*) = 0 \\ \alpha_i - \alpha_i^* \in [0, C] \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

Where C and ε are the chosen by the user.

The "kernel trick" is a means to convert a linear regression learning into a non-linear one by mapping the original observation samples into a higher-dimensional space, in order to account for non-linearities in the estimate function (Fig. 3.12). $k(x, y) = \langle \psi(x), \psi(y) \rangle$, where $\psi(x) : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow H$ and where H is a high-dimensional feature space with dot product. A

Figure 3.12: map the training data non linearly into a higher-dimensional feature space and construct a separating hyperplane with maximum margin.

commonly used kernel is the Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel:

$$k(x, y) = \exp(-\gamma \|x - y\|^2) \quad (3.9)$$

where the width parameter γ is selected by the user.

The Support Vector Regression algorithm allows us to find a non-linear mapping between high-level controls and the PC synthesis parameters. In the following section, we will show how to extract the audio features we use as controllers.

3.5 Feature extraction

We want to be able to predict the parameters of an additive synthesis model (output or target) from fundamental frequency, loudness and timbral features (input or controls). The machine learning component is in charge of learning and reproducing the acoustic properties of the particular instrument that is represented by the training database. In some way, it is learning a model of the timbre.

Figure 3.13: High-level control extraction

3.5.1 Controls/Inputs

The features are obtained from short-term additive analysis extracted with the SMSTools software based on the SMS model [Serra 1998]. We organize our data in a SDIF (Standard for Description and Exchange of Synthesis parameters) time-tagged frames [Wright et al. 1998]. Each frame is composed of the frequencies, amplitudes and phases of the quasi-harmonic components.

3.5.1.1 Spectral Analysis

The first step of a spectral analysis is to compute the magnitude and phase spectra of the different signal frames (Fig. 3.15). The computation of the spectra is done with the Short-term Fourier Transform (STFT), where the parameters to be chosen are the window size, the window type, the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) size and the frame rate.

Since here we decided to use an harmonic model for sake of simplicity, we are mostly concerned about the frequency resolution of our analysis (we don't take into account the stochastic component in our first approach), which means that the window size has to be large enough.

Figure 3.14: Visualization of the time-varying partial amplitudes in a SDIF files with *sdif-edit* software

We also need to track the partials of the audio signal in order to do the resynthesis. The next step to achieve our goal is to detect relevant peaks in the spectrum of each analysis frame .

A peak is defined as a local maximum in the magnitude spectrum (Fig. 3.16). For most instruments that are in fact not harmonic, the frequency representation of a stable sinusoid in a spectrum is not obvious, this is why the SMS technique first detect as many peaks as possible and later uses a peak continuation algorithm. The peak continuation algorithm relies on the notion of guides that advance in time through the spectral peaks (Fig. 3.17), and thus intends to replicate and extract the natural partial trajectories of a sound (see [Amatriain et al. 2002] for more details).

In practice, we chose the following parametrization: the analysis window (BlackmanHarris 92dB) size is 1024 samples. Hop size is 256 samples. The sampling rate 44100Hz. We kept 80 harmonics trajectories. Thus

Figure 3.15: Spectrum Computation: 1) packing the windowed sound signal in a fft buffer, 2) magnitude spectrum and 3) phase spectrum (from [Serra 1998])

Figure 3.16: Peak detection: 1) peaks in the magnitude spectrum 2) peaks in the phase spectrum (from [Serra 1998])

Figure 3.17: Peak continuation. g are the guides and p the spectral peaks (from [Serra 1998])

the time-varying partial amplitude matrix is of dimension 80 by number of frames.

This spectral analysis provides us with parameters from which high-level perceptual features can be extracted. For instance, fundamental frequency and loudness are continuous features (independent from timbre) we extract and use as controls for the synthesis.

3.5.1.2 Fundamental Frequency

Fundamental frequency is crucial for the quality of the resynthesis. We chose to use the Yin algorithm to extract an accurate fundamental frequency from the audio signal. The Yin method was inspired by auditory models of pitch perception, but is not a pitch perception model. It has been proven to be reliable, accurate and flexible on extensive testing on speech and musical sounds [Cheveigne 2002]. We had to carry out three main postprocessing tasks on the raw data given by the algorithm to obtain satisfying data sets for our application. First, based on the aperiodicity, and energy given by the YIN algorithm, the noisy data in the pitch track is “cleaned” as such: if the product of the normalized periodicity, power and coherence windows is inferior to 0.5, then the corresponding datapoints are removed.

In a second step, we use a median filter and interpolate pitch during unvoiced regions to produce a smooth pitch curve.

Finally, since the size of the analysis window for the Yin algorithm can be different from the SMS harmonic analysis window, we resample the result to match the difference in frameshifts. In practice, if we want a good estimate of the pitch, the algorithm needs to be fed with the range of variation of fundamental frequency.

Figure 3.18: Clean Fundamental Frequency Estimation

Figure 3.19: Smooth Fundamental Frequency Estimation

3.5.1.3 Loudness

We obtain a loudness estimate by applying a loudness summation model like those proposed by Zwicker and Scharf [Zwicker and Scharf 1965]:

$$I(n) = \sum_{k=1}^N a_k(n) \quad (3.10)$$

3.5.1.4 Continuous Timbre Descriptors

The exploration of fine timbral control is also possible. Our system is designed in such a way that it allows to “shape” the synthesis of a sound using any kind of continuous feature extracted from audio as a controller.

For instance, we can obtain a measure of brightness by computing the centroid or “center of gravity” for each spectral frame (relative energy at the high frequencies) [Grey and Gordon 1978][Wessel 1979].

$$SC(n) = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^N a_k \cdot f_k}{\sum_{k=1}^N a_k}(n) \quad (3.11)$$

We can mention that, often, increasing loudness also increases the amount of high spectrum content of a signal, which makes a sound brighter.

It is also possible to extract many other continuous features/descriptors of timbre such as those described in 2.3 on page 32. Traditionally, perceptual research on timbre has not put the emphasis on time-varying sonic features. The technique we present and develop in this document could serve as a powerful tool at this high-level time-varying feature-based timbre exploration. A more complete study of the continuous control over timbre synthesis from perceptual features is a subject that we plan to further develop in future research.

Finally, we have a high-level input vector of dimension two or more (At least loudness and fundamental frequency, and optionally other timbre

Figure 3.20: three-dimensional input vector: pitch, loudness, brightness

features) by number of frames (Fig. 3.20). The number of input analysis frame is synchronized with that of the output.

3.5.2 Targets/ Outputs

We have found a way to reduce the dimension of the target space with Principal Component Synthesis, and are able to resynthesize an estimate of the original sound from those Principal Component parameters without any significant perceptual loss. It is possible to choose the number of Principal Components to be kept by entering the percentage of variance of the data we wish to take into account. For example, in Fig. 3.21 we can see that most of the variance of our database is explained by only 3 PC. Therefore from now on, we can assume that our synthesis parameters lives in a 3D space for this dataset (Fig. 3.22), because we know we can reconstruct a good approximation of the original data (Fig. 3.23) from the

Figure 3.21: Pareto chart of the number of PCs against percentage of variance expressed

Principal Component analysis data. Our own good resynthesis results from the PC space confirm the results described in a previous complete perceptual study [Sandell and Martens 1995].

The dimension of the target vector is number of PCs by number of frame. Another advantage of PC analysis, besides dimensionality reduction, is that the new target vector components are uncorrelated, which is in general a good preprocessing practice for machine learning [Bishop 1995].

Even if we have reduced the dimensionality of the space, we based our reasoning on statistical principles. A human interactor could possibly control independently this lower dimensional PC parameter space, but those parameters do not necessarily have a relation to perception. We need another layer to map perceptual, intuitive, musically relevant controls to this lower dimensional synthesis parameter space. This task is handled by the Support Vector Regression (SVR) algorithm.

The following section deals with the practical aspects of training the learner that maps sonic percepts to sound generation parameters, while taking into account our Principal Component Synthesis model.

Figure 3.22: Test set trajectory in the PC space

3.6 Training and results

3.6.1 Database

We want the different inputs and outputs to be taken into account in the learning process independently of their units or variation range. To this purpose, we normalize the dataset so that it has zero mean and unity standard deviation.

In the case of the previous example of Fig.3.22, we end up with training examples of two-dimensional (fundamental and loudness) real-valued vector as input and three-dimensional (three PCs) real-valued vector as output.

In this particular example, the training set is extracted from an audio file of 2 minutes of solo saxophone with as much variability as possible in the attack, dynamics, range, etc...

To compute the error functions, we split the data we want to model into a training set and a testing set. (roughly 2/3, 1/3).

Figure 3.23: Reconstructed partial trajectories from the 3D PC space

Figure 3.24: Continuous Perceptual Controls: Fundamental Frequency, Loudness estimation and Brightness

The support vector regression algorithm we used in practice and described in [Chang and Lin 2001] works for only one output. It doesn't work as is for multiple outputs. Thus we have to split our problem into n distinct (and supposedly independent) function estimation problems, considering each time a different "PC trajectory" as output, n being the number of PC necessary for resynthesizing a sound without significant perceptual loss.

Once the controls and targets are defined, computed and standardized, we can start the training of the supervised machine learning algorithm.

3.6.2 Model selection

Resampling approaches, commonly used for SVM and other machine learning techniques, are very expensive in terms of computational costs and data requirements. Here, we have to deal with quite a lot of analysis samples. For example, just one minute of music generates 10336 analysis samples at 44.1KHz with a hop size of 256 samples. Luckily, we found in the literature, a new approach to parameter selection for support vector regression that is almost only analytical and that allows to tune the SVR parameters in an intuitive and non computationally expensive fashion.

The approach we used for parameter selection is based on a work by [Cherkassky and Ma 2004]. They propose a practical analytical approach to SVM regression parameter setting directly from the training data. "This method relies on theoretical understanding of SVM regression to provide the basic analytical form of dependencies for parameter selection. Further, it performs empirical tuning of such dependencies using several synthetic datasets". The different prescriptions for parameter selection are explained in the following paragraphs.

The optimal choice for the regularization parameter C is derived from the standard parametrization of the SVM solution.

We use the following prescription for regularization parameter:

$$C = \max(|\bar{y} + 3\sigma_y|, |\bar{y} - 3\sigma_y|) \quad (3.12)$$

Where \bar{y} is the mean of the training responses, and σ_y is the standard deviation of the training response.

The value of ε is chosen to be proportional to the input noise level. We assume that the standard deviation of noise σ can be estimated from data. For this purpose we used the k -nearest neighbours regression method proposed in [Cherkassky and Ma 2004].

We used their prescription for noise variance estimation via k -nearest neighbor's method:

$$\hat{\sigma}^2 = 1.5 \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (3.13)$$

where n is the number of training data, y_i the training response and \hat{y}_i the fit by the k -nn regression.

After empirical comparisons, [Cherkassky and Ma 2004] proposed the following dependency equation:

$$\varepsilon = \tau \sigma \sqrt{\frac{\ln n}{n}} \quad (3.14)$$

with $\tau = 3$ giving a good performance and σ is the noise standard deviation estimation, as defined in 3.13.

Finally, the kernel width is selected to roughly reflect the input range of the training/test data.

To summarize, we have obtained a semi-automatic parametrization of the SVR algorithm based on the dataset. This is an important and useful characteristics for a reproducible, reliable and automatic system for perceptual mapping.

3.6.3 Evaluation

For evaluating the performance of our system, we use two functional measures on the test dataset.

- The first one is the RMS error, which gives a measure of the overall distance between two trajectories

$$E_{rms} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_{test}} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{test}} (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2} \quad (3.15)$$

where y_i is the target original value, \hat{y}_i the estimation, and n_{test} the number of sample in the test dataset.

- The second measure is the correlation score, that indicates similarity of shape and synchrony between two trajectories.

$$r = \frac{\sum_i (\hat{y}_i - \bar{\hat{y}})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_i (\hat{y}_i - \bar{\hat{y}})^2 \sum_i (y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (3.16)$$

Finally, by resynthesis from the estimated output, we obtain a perceptual, subjective equivalent of those functional measures.

3.6.4 Results

The results of our experiment on the data extracted from saxophone solo recordings we described in section 3.6 are summarized in table 3.1. Figure 3.25 is a visualization of an excerpt of the training data, and figure 3.26 an excerpt of the test data. As can be seen, the estimation of the principal component trajectory on the test data (which controls have not been learned by the support vector machine before) is good (fig. 3.27) and the system generalizes well. Since we use a method for model selection that is based on the data (Section 3.6.2) and is semi-automatic, our approach is an improvement over the standard artificial neural network approaches ([Arfib et al. 2002, Wessel et al. 1998]).

Finally, the accuracy of our estimations is informally judged perceptively by hearing the results of sound synthesis. We find that the reproduction of the training data is perceptually lossless, whereas the generalization

Figure 3.25: Target and estimated first PC trajectory of the training set

Figure 3.26: Target and estimated first PC trajectories of the test set

PC trajectory	RMS error	Correlation score
First PC	0.009	0.991
Second PC	0.0159	0.982
Third PC	0.0534	0.973

Table 3.1: Results with a 2 min saxophone solo

Figure 3.27: Target/estimate correlation on the test set

to new controllers data still preserves the intrinsic characteristics of the original instrument (provided the new controllers are scaled to a range that corresponds to the limits of the instrument).

We also experimented with other databases (flute, voice, oboe, clarinet) of similar size and found almost identical accuracy in the estimations and synthesis sounding results. We didn't test this technique on non-sustained excitation instruments (piano for instance) since our system's goal is to put the emphasis on the ability to continuously control sounds. It makes more sense to focus on sustained excitation instruments for which the interaction is continuous, and for which imitative synthesis techniques are traditionally still lacking of realism and naturalness.

Those preliminary results look and sound very promising. We managed to synthesize realistic continuously excited instruments, where the controllers are based on perception. Nevertheless, our current implementation is non real-time which means that the "interactive quality" of the system can't be judge appropriately. We are working on a real-time implementation that will reveal the real potential of our paradigm, where musical intentions of the user will be instantaneously mapped to sound gen-

eration. Apart from this perceptual mapping layer, the different building blocks of our system are ready for real-time interaction (tangible and graphical interface, sound generation engine, etc. Cf. Appendix B).

3.7 Applications

3.7.1 Data-driven Synthesis

One of the most powerful feature of this system is its ability to change the original melody contour or loudness control while preserving the musical identity of the audio sequence on which the machine learning algorithm has been trained. The spectral properties of the sound are preserved when the control information varies, providing the new controls are rescaled in a similar range as the training data.

3.7.2 Interaction-based Synthesis for Sustained Excitation Instruments

Sound generation is a continuous timely process and many musical gestures are continuous. Nevertheless most of the tools commonly used for controlling sound synthesis (samplers, MIDI keyboards) are based on discrete event protocols. These models of control are relatively successful for instruments with low degree of interaction (piano for instance), but not for sustained excitation instruments that need a continuous control over sound synthesis parameters. We propose a synthesis system that allows for fine continuous control over sound generation which is based on auditory perception.

3.7.3 Pitch-shifting/ Time-warping

Our system allows to envision pitch shifting/time warping applications from a different angle. Because of the good generalization properties of the SVR algorithm, the musician can directly enter the desired time-varying frequency as a control input. The limitation of this technique is the range of the data on which the machine learning algorithm has been trained. The results will be poor if the frequencies given as an input to the system are too far from the frequencies encountered in the training set.

3.7.4 Cross-synthesis

Our model is well-suited for cross-synthesis, where the control parameters typical of one instrument can be used in combination with the “support vector timbre model” of another instrument.

Another possibility of cross-synthesis is at the level of the pc synthesis, where the PCs, or basis spectra, of one instrument can be replaced by those of another instrument.

3.7.5 Scalable Synthesis

Due to the characteristics of the PC synthesis, our model has an interesting property of scalability. The number of useful PC bases can be chosen depending on the quality of the sound required at the moment. This behavior is particularly interesting in networked applications, where the available bandwidth is variable.

3.7.6 Continuous Control over Timbre

In this paper we have mostly studied the control of a synthesis model from loudness and fundamental frequency parameters, letting the ma-

chine learning component take care of the overall timbre generation. But we have also managed to control directly the properties of an instrument timbre such as brightness. This property, allowing direct generation of sound from continuous timbral features, is extremely interesting, and suggests an analysis-by-synthesis type of applications. Traditionally, perceptual research on timbre has not put the emphasis on time-varying sonic features. The technique we present and develop in this document could serve as a powerful tool a this high-level time-varying feature-based timbre exploration. For instance, in the Music Information Retrieval community, the problem of finding relevant descriptors and judging their perceptual influence is still open. Our tool allowing feature-based synthesis would prove useful.

3.7.7 Other

Musical systems such as intuitive and "intelligent" synthesizers, interfaces, etc. but also multimedia systems in general (synthesizer of sound effects for movies, context-based video games, sonification...) constitute a field of study where synthesis from high-level descriptors finds numerous applications. This research is also related to the notions of structured audio and audio description and indexing investigated in the MPEG-4 [Scheirer 1998] and MPEG-7 [Hyoung et al. 2006] normalization processes.

3.8 Summary

In this Chapter, we presented our view on the problem of mapping in computer-based music instrument. Based on the literature and the conclusions drawn from our state of the art of Chapter 2, we focused on perceptual mapping, where the sound generation engine is controlled by perceptually meaningful high-level parameters. After presenting the

general architecture of our system, we described what we call the Principal Component Synthesis model, which is based on an additive synthesis model enhanced with principal component analysis. Then, we presented a Support Vector Regression algorithm for automatic mapping from controllers to sound synthesis parameters. The next section was dedicated to the definition of the system's inputs and outputs, and the practical extraction of features for control and synthesis parameter estimation. We then explained how to train, tune, and evaluate the machine learning component of our model, and finally presented different applications that stem from the possibility of mapping intuitive sonic percepts to sound generation models.

Chapter 4

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

4.1 Contributions

In this research report, we gave an overview of different sound generation models, and compared their respective merits for our perceptual synthesizer paradigm approach. It appeared that spectral and physical models were the most interesting and flexible techniques for our purposes, and we decided to start by studying high-level mappings to an additive model parameters.

We also introduced various approaches to describing sounds. Since listeners have a tendency to naturally describe sounds at the perceptual level rather than at the signal level, we put the emphasis on sound descriptors that are related to perceptive attributes of sounds such as loudness, pitch, spectral centroid, spectral spread, or physical parameters such as volume, elasticity, etc. We also showed that albeit useful for describing any arbitrary sounds, some of Schaeffer taxonomy's descriptors weren't really suited for a continuous control of synthesis parameters.

Additionally, we proposed a classification of techniques for mapping high-level controllers to sound synthesis parameters and justified our choice

of a machine learning approach by its generality and independence towards sound synthesis models. Consequently, it is also possible to reuse our framework with a synthesis paradigm that is not based on spectral modelling.

In a second time, we proposed a framework and described the architecture we used for the implementation of our system. This system's goal is to allow for flexible and intuitive control of sound generation from high-level sonic percepts. It provides the user with continuous control over a sound directly analyzed from recordings.

To attain our goal, we devised an analysis/synthesis model based on the additive spectral model and Principal Component Analysis. This model is well-suited for a machine learning approach to our specific non-linear mapping problem. As a matter of fact Principal Component Analysis proved to be an efficient way to reduce the dimensionality of the synthesis parameter space, while preserving the auditory quality of the resynthesis. This allowed us to have to train only a lower number of regressors for realizing the mapping between controllers and low-dimensional principal component trajectories (typically of order 10).

We described a complete and coherent framework to train, tune and evaluate our system in an automatic, consistent and reproducible fashion. The mapping from high-level descriptors (such as pitch estimation based on the yin algorithm, loudness and brightness estimations) to principal component trajectories was achieved using Support Vector Regression. The model selection was done analytically, from the training dataset, and allowed us to tune the SVR parameters in an intuitive and non-computationally expensive manner. This is an improvement over the other machine learning methods such as artificial neural networks that had previously been applied to similar non-linear mapping problems. Additionally, compared to other regression methods the results of SVR are stable, reproducible, and eliminate the problem of local minima. We proposed criteria of evaluation of our results based on the RMS error and correlation score between the estimated trajectories and the real trajectories of a testing data set.

On our reduced data set, the results were promising and this novel kind of architecture yielded various original audio and musical applications.

4.2 Improvements

The results of this preliminary work are based on relatively small databases. In the future, we would like to extend our experiments with the actual system on larger datasets including as much variance as possible. We should try our algorithms on many different type of sustained excitation instruments for which the control and interaction is continuous. We'd like to study how the size of the database influence the quality of the resynthesis when the system is presented to unseen controller values.

The work presented in this dissertation did not include a memory mechanism for previous states of an instrument. We know, for example, that in a rapid passage, a given note on a wind instrument will sound different depending on whether it was preceded by a higher or lower pitch. Future work should model and study the influence of these temporal dependencies. Prior state can be easily introduced into the machine learning architecture. A qualitative study of the influence of a memory mechanism on the quality of the synthesis could be pursued.

At the time of this writing, the analysis and synthesis of sounds are realized off-line. Nevertheless, the synthesis models presented are causal and can be implemented in real-time. Future research and musical application will benefit greatly from real-time interaction between the musician and this new smart instrument. One of the main motivation behind this project was to be able to improve interaction between the user/musician and the sound synthesizer. A real-time implementation of the system is being carried on using the open-source pure-data framework for building externals [Puckette 1997].

Another possible future direction of research is the application of some other more advanced techniques for dimension reduction such as Inde-

pendent Component Analysis (ICA), Kernel PCA (KPCA) [Scholkopf et al. 1998]. In our problem's case, the amplitude matrix is non-negative, so Non-Negative Matrix Factorization (NNMF) and Non-Negative Independent Component Analysis (NNICA) could also be used to compute basis vectors for low-dimensional models of the amplitude matrix. The detailed study of their respective merits and efficiency for sound synthesis is a subject we'd like to investigate in future works.

This dissertation's modular model is easily adaptable to future changes. It is possible to add/modify new inputs, outputs and various refined synthesis models while preserving the general architecture of the original system. We could for instance improve on the perceptual controllers by replacing fundamental frequency by pitch, or the intensity summary by another loudness estimation. Also, we can easily add other continuous descriptors of timbre as input such as those described in section 2.3. Traditionally, perceptual research on timbre has not put the emphasis on time-varying sonic features. The techniques we present and develop in this report proves to be a powerful tool in a high-level time-varying feature-based timbre exploration. We would like to realize a more complete and systematic study of the continuous control over timbre synthesis from perceptual features. Finally, we should also study the validity of our paradigm to control other type of synthesis algorithms such as physical models for instance.

Another possibility of extension of our work is to apply the concepts we developed in this dissertation to the control of higher-level musical structures. Our work so far dealt only with the control of sound synthesis, but it would be interesting to generate musical structures from perceptual controllers too. For instance in [Manzolini and Verschure], the authors devised a robot that produces musical events based on the data collected by sensors that give some information about the room where they are situated. The idea is to give some information on the state of the room by transmitting meaningful musical messages representing specific moods or emotional states. (For example, if the room is too full, the robot produces aggressive music to make people leave, etc.) We would have to find

a set of perceptual controllers and generative algorithms that are relevant for the generation of complex, interesting and “meaningful” musical structures.

No matter what improvements will be made to the actual framework, the flexibility and modularity of our system ensures a reliable tool for the development of creative expression. We believe that our system could improve greatly with further research and development. Along the way to investigating the problem of perceptual mapping for sound synthesis, we were confronted to new challenges and fundamental questions related to the coupling between action and perception in the auditory domain. This possible future axis of investigation will be briefly presented in the following section.

4.3 Interactive Computer Based Instruments and the Sensorimotor System

In the research we previously described, we focused our efforts on devising a model for human interaction with a computer-based sound synthesizer, where the interaction is based on perceptual controllers. A potentially promising future investigation would be to study and model the sensory-motor system constituted by the human interactor itself. By analyzing dynamic relations between perception and action we could understand better how the development of perceptual abilities can modify the development of actions, and how the development of actions can modify the development of perceptual abilities.

Performing music requires fast auditory and motor processing. Regarding professional musicians, recent brain imaging studies have demonstrated that auditory stimulation produces a co-activation of motor areas, whereas silent tapping of musical phrases evokes a co-activation in auditory regions. Perceptual systems are usually studied separately from motor systems, but there are strong arguments in favor of merging the

Figure 4.1: Computer-based Performance Framework

two, or at least, for including the dimension of action within the study of perception.

The study of perception and action in the auditory domain seems to be a bit underdeveloped compared to the field of vision for instance. “It has been argued that visual information is not accrued by sampling successive 2D patterns from the retina, but rather from the interplay between sensory changes and eye, body and environmental movements. The structure of three-dimensional space can be "learned" from the cross-correlation between movement and sensory information. It has even been claimed that perceptual is, to some degree, stored internally in the form "potential actions", ready to be performed as soon as ceases the inhibitory mechanisms that keep them in check. The technological counterpart is, in robotics, the joint development of sensory and motor functions, or the "calibration" of delicate control mechanisms based on sensory feedback.”[Cheveigne 2005]

Similarly to vision we could apply the same methodology to the audio domain since the musician and its instrument form an overall adaptive system [Lee and Wessel 1992]. This question is especially interesting for interactive musical performance. The musician's intentions are refined and defined by the discovery of new possibilities of the instrument [Wessel and Wright 2001]. The study of how the motor program is developed and the importance of the matching between actions and auditory feedback is a fundamental subject and a potential interesting direction for future research. For instance, there are some inspiring models that come from the motor control research community [Jordan and Rumelhart 1992] and suggests that people use an “internal model of the consequences of actions to help guide actions which could be applied and adapted to the study of perception-action in the context of a computer-based interactive musical performance.

Our initial idea was to devise a general framework that would allow the control of sound synthesis in an intuitive way, based on state-of-the-art knowledge of human auditory perception and cognition. This interdisciplinary problem embraces a lot of different connex areas, and raised

many interesting fundamental questions. We only scratched the surface of what we believe is a fascinating area of research. In the future, we hope to further explore the rich field of computer-based music and sound analysis / generation, with a focus on perception and action.

Appendix A

INTERFACES FOR CONTROLLING SOUND GENERATION

THIS appendix gives a quick overview of the different types of interfaces for the control of sound synthesis. After giving a description of the most common graphical interfaces available in musical applications, we introduce physical interfaces and finally, in Annex B, we describe a musical physical interface we built for our system. In the previous chapters of this report, we devised a means to build sounds from perceptually-based continuous controls. This annex is documenting the various ways one can reify these perceptual controllers we extracted into graphical or tangible controllers.

Personal Computers have democratized the field of computer music. Nowadays such tasks as the control and programming of synthesizers via the MIDI or OSC protocol, sampling, audio editing, real time audio processing, formalization and transformation of musical structures, sound synthesis, and acoustic simulation have become common and easily accessible in relatively cheap commercial software. The development of those software tools have developed in parallel with Graphical User Interfaces (GUI).

The model we are dealing with here refers to a specific environment of human-computer interaction, namely a display, a mouse, a keyboard and the possibility to listen to the audio output via loudspeakers or headphones. The general principles have been theorized by Doug Engelbart, and are known under the acronym WIMP for Windows, Icons, Menus and Pointing.

The study of interfaces for musical processes is specific in the sense that they are a visual counterpart of a sound process. A first distinction is between instantaneous or sequenced interfaces. The apprehension of a visual scene is almost instantaneous, whereas an auditory scene is developing in time. Another distinction is between static and dynamic. It's often mostly in a static way that image is used in graphical interfaces for audio. Principal changes in the display results from a user action. Moreover, it is possible to represent visually the localization of sound sources, although auditive localization is more imprecise than the visual one [Vinet and Delalande 1999].

We follow the typology proposed by Vinet: the first type of interface consists of virtual control objects. They are the figurative representation of physical objects. Some examples are: potentiometers, buttons, Boolean interpolation between parameters as used in the Syter system by INAGRM for instance, Gaussian Mixture models for parameters interpolation [Momeni and Wessel 2003], sound spatialization in virtual spaces with virtual sources, control panels reproducing old analog synthesizer panels, etc. The idea is to reproduce virtually (graphically) the comportment of a real physical control. They are controlling parameters in real-time.

A second type of graphical interface is related to temporal representation. It includes a spatial dimension related to time. The most common representation is a horizontal axis for time, and vertical axis for synchronous events. A very popular interface for musical (MIDI) representation is the Piano Roll. Other representation for audio signal are tables, breakpoint functions, envelopes, sonograms, ... Finally there is a lot of sequencer-like interfaces, based on multipist recording devices.

Figure A.1: My tremolo effect GUI in Qt with OSC communication

Figure A.2: The same tremolo effect GUI in PD

Another interesting paradigm is that of graphical programming languages. This paradigm provides a more abstract representation of audio processing. The descriptions of synthesis algorithms are called patches, which are composed of interconnected modules that generate and transform signals. For example, an oscillator module generates a signal, and an envelope module applies an amplitude modulation to the signal to form a note.

Graphical interfaces based on the WIMP paradigm tend to reach their limits nowadays. Each new piece of software comes with new interface objects, longer menus, longer dialog boxes, etc. There is a trend in new interface research that aims at reducing the complexity of WIMP interfaces, by “reducing interfaces to augment interaction”. (gesture interaction, bimanual interaction, augmented reality,...)

Jean Piaget in his studies about cognitive development says there are three stages of learning in human development: enactive, iconic, and symbolic thinking (Fig. A.3). The enactive or kinesthetic knowledge is our ability to grasp, suck, etc. The iconic thinking is related to how things look. For instance, if an object look bigger, we have a tendency to associate it with the concept “more”. Finally, symbolic thinking comes from the basic understanding of conservation such as in a mathematical expression $a = b$.

Typically, the development of human computer interfaces have followed the opposite path, from symbolic (tty) to iconic (mouse and bitmap display). The next step in the development of computer interfaces should indeed be enactive interfaces (Physical, or Tangible User Interfaces). With this in mind, we devised a possible physical interface for the perceptual synthesizer we described in the previous chapters of this report. At the difference of graphical interfaces for which there exist various development toolkits (Qt by Trolltech for instance), there is not really any well established toolkits for physical interfaces. Instead of giving an overview of existing paradigms and examples of tangible user interfaces, we wanted to see how it would be possible to build our own. Our experimental setup is described in Annex B.

Figure A.3: Three stages of learning (from Bill Verplank in [Ju and Wright 2005])

Appendix B

BASIC EXPERIMENTS IN TANGIBLE INTERFACE DESIGN

In the previous chapters we focused our efforts on devising a model for human interaction with a computer-based sound synthesizer, where the interaction is based on perceptual controllers. Here, we document our attempt at building a physical interface that could be used to control our sound synthesizer. The field of tangible interfaces is vast, fast growing and the musical applications of Tangible User Interfaces (TUI) would deserve a complete chapter. Here we don't pretend to give an overview of the field, nor a particularly novel design idea, but just a quick introduction to the practical aspects of building physical interfaces. This Appendix is just a starting point that summarizes and exemplify some information we have collected on interactive instrument design. In the future we are planning to build and use more complex interfaces to control our synthesizer based on perceptual synthesis paradigm.

Our purpose was to gain some kind of practical knowledge on physical interface design. We first gives some basic information on musical instrument design and then describes the set up of the practical project we realized.

Possible sources of feedback in a 250A project:

Figure B.1: Feedback (From M. Wright [Ju and Wright 2005])

B.1 Structural Overview

The first thing to think of is *what actions* the user will make and how it will control the sound output. The usual processing chain is: the user makes an action that is sensed by the sensors, that transmit the signal through circuits to a microcontroller (in our case the Atmel AVR microcontroller ATmega16). Those control information are then processed in PureData [Puckette 1997] to finally give the sounding result through loudspeakers. All the elements of this chain can be a source of feedback too.

The different elements in the chain will talk to each other with different signals (Open Sound Control messages, voltage, electrical signals, etc.)

B.2 The Project

We describe the different aspects of the projects based on the framework for interaction design proposed by Verplank:

Idea: The main idea of the project is to be able to navigate in a synthesized sound space in real-time.

Connections between the components of a typical 250A project:

Figure B.2: Connectivity (From M. Wright [Ju and Wright 2005])

Metaphor: The metaphor is that of a real physical 2D space representing a perceptual sound space, that the user can explore with one finger.

Model: The model is that of a flexible wooden square with sensors at each corner that can be used to sense pressure and position of a finger.

Display: There is a visual display (on a computer screen) that gives visual feedback on the physical state of the square (deformation and finger position) by means of a virtual dynamical physical model of the real structure.

Scenario: This project main purpose is to be used in real-time, as a live instrument.

Control: The controls are finger pressure and position on the square for the right hand, and distance for the left hand.

B.3 Data acquisition on the AVR Microcontroller

The microcontroller of choice for this project is the ATmega16 from ATMEL, which is a 8 bits processor. In this section, we give some basic information on the structure and functions of this microcontroller. Some details about the reason for choosing this microprocessor can be found in [Wilson et al. 2003].

Information from the program memory, the timer information, the state of I/O pins is stored in registers. In a 8 bit processor, register can hold 8 bits (bytes). Each register has an address in memory. A byte (8 bits) is represented by a two-digit hexadecimal number.

The 32 pins of ATmega16 are divided into 4 ports of 8 pins (PORT A, B, C D) represented by 4 bytes. Each physical I/O pin corresponds to a logical bit on the port. Setting is assigning a logical high value (1). Clearing is assigning a logical low value (0). Each I/O pin can be either input or output. This information is stored in the Data Direction Register (DDR).

In the ATmega16, PORT A can be bi-directional digital I/O or can be used for analog input (reading sensors data). To switch between analog and digital input, ADCSR register is used and set using specific C language libraries.

The good thing about choosing this microcontroller is that the programming of the ATmega16 is done in the C language. Some specifically designed libraries makes the development on the AVR fairly easy and fast, so it is relatively easy to acquire the data coming from the sensors through Port A (Force Sensing Resistor, Infra Red, Slider), or port B (buttons). Moreover, there exists an OSCSerial library that allows to transmit these data via the serial port of a computer in the OSC format [Wright et al. 2003].

The communication with the microcontroller is done via the serial port. The protocol chosen for this seminar is a port of the Open Sound Con-

Figure B.3: Sensor Chain [Ju and Wright 2005]

trol for serial communication. Open Sound Control is a protocol which original goal is to control sound synthesis applications. It can be used as a replacement to MIDI, but also support a hierarchy of messages that are bound to different receivers. It is actually open and general enough so that it can be used to communicate between computers, sound synthesizers, and any other multimedia device. In our project, this protocol is used to communicate between the microcontroller, processing control information, and Pure Data synthesizing interactive media in real time.

Hence, the first step of acquiring and transmitting to and from the microcontroller is handled quite seamlessly.

B.4 Modules

Once the microcontroller has been programmed to receive the data from the sensors and we have sent them via OSC [Wright et al. 2003] messages to the serial port of a computer, the data is finally sent to Pure Data (PD) [Puckette 1997], a real-time dataflow language. The structure of our interface is pretty straightforward. First we built a PD patch that retrieves the sensor data and processes it. Then, we built another PD patch for 3D visual feedback, and finally a MaxMSP patch has been designed for additive sound synthesis. We chose to implement the real-time synthesis engine in Max-MSP because Pure Data doesn't support the SDIF standard yet, and all our synthesis data is formatted following this tagged frame standard [Wright et al. 1998]. PD patches communi-

Figure B.4: Sketch of the Physical Interface

cate to each others via OSC messages. PD and Max/MSP patches communicate via OSC message over the network (the synthesis engine and the control interface are on different machines.)

The main patch gets control data from the AVR microprocessor, processes it and send it to Max-MSP for synthesis.

B.4.0.1 Sensor data

There are four different types of control data received from the sensors and routed via OSC messages to the Pure Data interface.

The first type of control data is received via the OSCroute message /button, and allows for choosing different playing modes of the instrument the user can choose by pushing a toggle button. Buttons are one of the simplest sensors. They open or close the flow of electrons through a branch of an electric circuit.

The second control is received via /F1, /F2, /F3, /F4. It corresponds to the pressure sensed by 4 Force Sensing Resistors (FSRs) situated at each corner of our square control surface. FSRs are made of 2 parts. The first is a resistive material applied to a film. The second is a set of digitating contacts applied to another film. The resistive material serves to make an electrical path between the two sets of conductors on the other film. When a force is applied, a better connection is made between the contacts and the conductivity is increased. In the linear area, the force is proportional to $1/R$. After a threshold is passed, there is saturation, and a variation of force doesn't imply any variation in the resistance. FSR are not appropriate for accurate measurements of force because different items can have as much as 25% variation between each other, but are sufficient for our purposes.

The third channel of sensor data is received via /IR, and corresponds to a reflective optical sensor that gives a range value measuring the distance of the left hand to the distance Infrared sensor. The sensor consists of

an infrared led and a phototransistor that passes an amount of current proportional to the reflected light received.

The last control data is received via /slider, and is just a continuous slider value used to control the main volume of the sound generation engine. The sensor is basically a potentiometer or variable resistor controlled by the position of the slider.

B.4.0.2 Graphical Interface

The interface is divided into different areas and each area has its specific functionality. The first part is related to data conditioning, and gives control on how the data coming from the sensors is processed. We get the information from the four FSR situated at each corner of the wooden square control surface to deduce the position and the pressure exerted by a finger on that square. The FSR signal processing includes filtering in the audio domain. The IR data is also filtered in the audio domain. The second area is used to visualize what values are received by the sensors (Fig. B.6). The third area deals with the set up for sending the control information from the sensors to the synthesizer (we can choose whether the synthesizer is on a local or remote machine communicating via ethernet). Finally, the fourth area deals with sending the control information from FSR's to a 3D visualization module.

B.4.1 Visual feedback

We implemented a module that gives visual feedback on the state of the four FSR sensors. A structure (in our case a square made of flexible wood) is modeled virtually by a combination of masses and springs that interact with each others. Values of FSR sensors are received in the module and used to excite the virtual 3D structure (Fig. B.7).

The rendering style, position of the figure, and physical properties of the virtual structure are all configurable (Fig. B.8). This module is using the

Figure B.5: The Tangible Interface Prototype

Figure B.6: My GUI for displaying the values of the different sensors in real-time

Figure B.7: Virtual 3D representation of the tangible control surface representing in real-time the pressure exerted on each FSR at the corner of the physical wooden square. Here we can see that 3 FSR out of 4 are measuring some significant pressure from the user.

Figure B.8: My GUI for controlling the display of the 3D openGL virtual surface

Gem library in Pure Data allowing to control open GL graphics in real-time. Each node on the grid corresponds to a mass and each segment to a spring.

B.4.2 Auditory Feedback/Sound Synthesis

Finally, a Max-MSP patch synthesizer receives the control data via OSC through the network on another machine dedicated to real-time synthesis, and maps it to synthesis parameters. The position of the finger on the physical square control interface can be used to interpolate between different timbral synthesis parameters and/or to control pitch (different modes are available). Finger pressure information is used to control the loudness of the synthesis. If the finger doesn't touch the surface, no sound is output. IR information is used to control pitch, or timbral modulation, depending on the instrument mode, and the slider value controls the main volume.

Although our tangible interface is still relatively basic, this project was a good introduction to designing interactive systems from a bottom up approach. The natural haptic feedback from the thin and flexible wooden control surface proved to be quite enjoyable, and the 3D virtual visual feedback gave us an interesting cue on the state of the synthesis parameters. This interface used in a real musical context was intuitive and easy to play with. An important missing part for the whole system to

be a fully interesting and complex instrument is the real-time perceptual mapping layer we described in the previous chapters of this dissertation. This project allowed us to acquire a lot of practical experience in the design of physical interface, and proved that we could “easily” build our own customized interfaces to sound synthesizers. In the future we wish to develop more complex and interesting tangible interfaces that would suit well our design ideas on perceptual mappings.

Appendix C

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

SOME of the previously-mentioned acronyms are sorted alphabetically below. They should be used as a reference.

ANN: Artificial Neural Network

DDR: Data Direction Register

FM: Frequency Modulation

FSR: Force Sensing Resistor

GUI: Graphical User Interface

I/O: Input/Output

ICA: Independant Component Analysis

IDA: Intelligent Data Analysis

IR: Infra Red

KPCA: Kernel Principal Component Analysis

MIDI: Musical Instrument Digital Interface

NNMF: Non-negative Matrix Factorization

OSC: Open Sound Control

PC: Principal Component

PCA: Principal Component Analysis

PD: Pure Data

SDIF: Sound Description Interchange Format

SMS: Spectral Modelling Synthesis

SVM: Support Vector Machine

SVR: Support Vector Regression

TUI: Tangible User Interface

WIMP: Windows Icon Menu and Pointing

Appendix D

PUBLICATIONS

Journals

- Cano, P. Koppenberger, M. Le Groux, S. Ricard, J. Wack, N. Herrera, P. 2005. 'Nearest-Neighbor Automatic Sound Classification with a WordNet Taxonomy' *Journal of Intelligent Information Systems*; Vol.24 .2 99-111

Conferences

- Pedro Cano, M. K., Sylvain Le Groux, Perfecto Herrera, Julien Ricard, Nicolas Wack (2004). Knowledge and Content-Based Audio Retrieval Using Wordnet. ICETE, Setubal, Portugal.
- Cano, P. K., M. Le Groux, S. Ricard, J. Herrera, P. Wack (2004). Semantic and Perceptual Management of Sound Effects in Production Systems. *Proceedings of International Broadcasting Conference*, Amsterdam, The Netherlands.
- Cano, P. K., M. Le Groux, S. Ricard, J. Herrera, P. Wack (2004). Nearest-neighbor generic sound classification with a wordnet-based taxonomy. *Proceedings of AES 116th Convention*, Berlin, Germany.

Academic

- Le Groux, S. (2002). Artificial Neural Networks for Expressive Control of Musical Sounds. DEA in Acoustics, Electrical Engineering, Computer Science and Music, Paris 6, France and U.C.Berkeley, California, USA: 70.
- Le Groux, S. (2001). Scalable Sound Synthesis. Department of Electronic Engineering. Masters in Signal Processing, King's College, University of London: 54.

Talks

- Le Groux, S. (2004). Extraction of relevant controllers for the analysis by synthesis of musical sounds. ISMIR Conference, Barcelona.
- Le Groux, S. (2006) "Mappings from perception to sound generation", Summer School in Sound and Music Computing, s2s², Barcelona

Bibliography

- [Amatriain et al. 2002] Amatriain, X. Bonada, J. Loscos, A. Serra, X. "Chapter 10. Spectral Processing" in DAFX: Digital Audio Effects, Udo Zoelzer (ed.). pp. 554. John Wiley & Sons Ed. 2002
- [Arfib et al. 2002] Arfib, D., Couturier, J. M., Kessous, L., and Verfaillie, V. 2002. Strategies of mapping between gesture data and synthesis model parameters using perceptual spaces. *Org. Sound* 7, 2 (Aug. 2002), 127-144.
- [AudioClas] AudioClas: a European Eureka project. <http://audioclas.iua.upf.edu>
- [Aulay and Quatieri 1986] R. Mc Aulay and Th. Quatieri, "Speech analysis/synthesis based on a sinusoidal representation", *IEEE Trans. On Acoust., Speech, and Signal Proc.*, vol. ASSP-34, August 1986.
- [Bennett and Campbel 2000] J. C. Bennett, C. Campbel, "Support Vector Machines: Hype or Hallelujah?", *SIGKDD Explorations*, Vol. 2, No. 2, 1-13, 2000.

- [Bishop 1995] C. M. Bishop. *Neural Networks for Pattern Recognition*. Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1995.
- [Charbonneau et al. 1997a] Charbonneau, G., Hourdin, C. and Moussa, T. 1997a. A Multidimensional Scaling Analysis of Musical Instrumentsâ Time-Varying Spectra. *Computer Music Journal* 21 (2): 40-55.
- [Charbonneau et al. 1997b] Charbonneau, G., Hourdin, C. and Moussa, T. (1997b). A Sound Synthesis Technique Based on Multidimensional Scaling of Spectra. *Computer Music Journal* 21 (2): 56-68.
- [Chang and Lin 2001] Chih-Chung Chang and Chih-Jen Lin, LIBSVM : a library for support vector machines, 2001. Software available at <http://www.csie.ntu.edu.tw/~cjlin/libsvm> The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America – July 1981 – Volume 70, Issue 1, p. 262
- [Cherkassky and Ma 2004] Cherkassky, V. and Ma, Y. 2004. Practical selection of SVM parameters and noise estimation for SVM regression. *Neural Netw.* 17, 1 (Jan. 2004), 113-126.
- [Cheveigne 2002] de Cheveigne, A., and Kawahara, H. (2002). "YIN, a fundamental frequency estimator for speech and music," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*
- [Cheveigne 2005] Cheveigne de, A. (2005) *Scientific and Technological Roadmap in Sound and Music Computing*. <http://www.soundandmusiccomputing.org/>

- [Cherkassky and Ma 2004] Cherkassky, V. and Ma, Y. 2004. Practical selection of SVM parameters and noise estimation for SVM regression. *Neural Netw.* 17, 1 (Jan. 2004), 113-126.
- [Fletcher 1940] H. Fletcher, "Auditory patterns", *Revs Modern Physics*, 12, pp. 47-65, 1940.
- [Fletcher and Munson 1933] H. Fletcher and W. A. Munson. "Loudness, its definition, measurement and calculation" in *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* 5, 82-108 (1933).
- [Gaver 1993] William W. Gaver, How do we hear in the world? Explorations in ecological acoustics, & *Ecological Psychology*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 285-313, 1993.
- [Grey and Gordon 1978] Grey J. M., and J. W. Gordon 1978. "Perceptual Effects of Spectral Modifications on Musical Timbres." *Journal of Acoustical Society of America* 63(5): 1493-1500
- [Gazzaniga 2000] Gazzaniga, M.S. (2000). *The new cognitive neurosciences*. MIT Press, Cambridge, Mass.
- [Grey 1975] J. M. Grey. *An Exploration of Musical Timbre*. PhD thesis, Department of Psychology, Stanford University, 1975.
- [Hunt et al. 2000] Hunt, A., Wanderley, M., Kirk, R. Towards a Model for Instrumental Mapping in Expert Musical Interaction. *Proc. of the International Computer Music Conference*, 2000.

- [Hyoungh et al. 2006] Hyoungh-Gook Kim, Thomas Sikora, Nicholas Moreau, Nicolas Moreau MPEG-7 Audio and Beyond: Audio Content Indexing and Retrieval, Wiley and son ed. 2006.
- [Jackson 1991] Jackson JE A User's Guide to Principal Components New York:Wiley. 1991.
- [Jehan and Schoner 2001] T. Jehan and B. Schoner, "An audio-driven perceptually meaningful timbre synthesizer," in Proc. Int. Computer Music Conf., (Havana, Cuba), 2001
- [Jordan and Jacobs 1994] Jordan, M. I., & Jacobs, R. A. (1994). Hierarchical mixtures of experts and the EM algorithm. *Neural Computation*, 6, 181-214.
- [Jordan and Rumelhart 1992] Jordan, M. I. and Rumelhart, D. (1992). Forward models: Supervised learning with a distal teacher. *Cognitive Science*, 16:307–354.
- [Ju and Wright 2005] Ju, W. and Wright, M. 2005. Musical Interface Design Workshop. CCRMA. Stanford University
- [Lee and Wessel 1992] M. A. Lee and D. Wessel, "Connectionist models for real-time control of synthesis and compositional algorithms," *Proceedings of the International Computer Music Conference*, 1992.
- [Manzolli and Verschure] Manzolli, J and Verschure PFMJ 2005. Roboser: a Real-World Composition System. *Computer Music Journal* .

- [McAdams and Bigand 1993] McAdams, and Bigand. *Thinking in Sound: The Cognitive Psychology of Human Audition*. Oxford University Press, 1993.
- [McAdams et al. 1995] Stephen McAdams, S. Winsberg, S. Donnadieu, G. De Soete, and J. Krimphoff. Perceptual scaling of synthesized musical timbres: common dimensions, specificities and latent subject classes. *Psychological reserach*, 58:177–192, 1995. 327
- [Mathews 1969] Mathews, M.: *The Technology of Computer Music*. MIT Press, 1969.
- [Moore 1990] F.R. Moore, *Elements for Computer Music*, Prentice Hall, 1990.
- [Momeni and Henry 2006] Ali Momeni and Cyrille Henry. "Dynamic Independent Mapping Layers for Concurrent Control of Audio and Video Synthesis". *Computer Music Journal*, 30:1, pp. 49-66, Spring 2006
- [Momeni and Wessel 2003] Momeni, A. and D. Wessel, *Characterizing and Controlling Musical Material Intuitively with Graphical Models*, *Proceedings of the New Interfaces for Musical Expression Conference*, Montreal, Canada, 2003. 88
- [Mynatt 1994] Elizabeth D. Mynatt, *Designing with auditory icons*, in *CHI '94*, Boston, Massachusetts, 1994, ACM.
- [Nilsson 1999] Nilsson, Nils J., *Introduction to Machine Learning (Draft version)*, Department of

- Computer Science, Stanford University. 1999.
- [Paula and Loureiro 2001] Paula, HB; Loureiro, Mauricio Alves. Sonological Representation of a Musical Instrument by Sub-spaces of Spectral Components. *Mikropolyphonie*, v. 7, 2001
- [Peeters et al. 2000] Geoffroy Peeters, Stephen McAdams, and Perfecto Herrera. Instrument sound description in the context of MPEG-7. In *Proc. Int. Comp. Music Conf. (ICMC)*, Berlin, Germany, 2000.
- [Peeters 2003] G. Peeters, Audio Features Extractions, Tech. report, Project CUIDADO, 2003.
- [Pfordresher 2005] Pfordresher, P. Q. 2005. Coordination of perception and action in music performance. *Advances in Experimental Psychology*.
- [Puckette 1988] Puckette, M. 1988. "The Patcher," *Proceedings, ICMC*. San Francisco: International Computer Music Association, pp. 420-429.
- [Puckette 1997] Puckette, S. M., "Pure data." *Proceedings of the International Computer Music Conference*, pp. 224–227, 1997.
- [Rasch and Plomp 1982] Rasch, R.A., & Plomp, R. (1982) The perception of musical tones. In D. Deutsch (Ed.), *The Psychology of Music* (pp. 1-24). New York: Academic Press.
- [Risset and Wessel 1982] Jean-Claude Risset et Wessel: "Exploration of Timbre by Analysis and Synthe-

- sis", *The Psychology of Music*, Deutsch eds. Orlando Academics, 1982.
- [Robel 1997] A. Robel. Neural network modeling of speech and music signals. In *Neural Information Processing Systems 9 (NIPS 96)*, pages 779–785, 1997.<http://citeseer.ist.psu.edu/robel96neural.html>
- [Rovan et al. 1997] J. Rován, M. Wanderley, S. Dubnov and P. Depalle, "Instrumental Gestural Mapping Strategies as Expressivity Determinants in Computer Music Performance", *KANSEI - The Technology of Emotion*, AIMI International Workshop, Genova
- [Sandell and Martens 1995] Sandell, G. and Martens, W. "Perceptual Evaluation of Principal-Component-Based Synthesis of Musical Timbres". *JAES* Volume 43 Number 12 pp. 1013-1028; December 1995
- [Schaeffer 1966] Schaeffer, P. (1966). *Traite des Objets Musicaux*. Paris: Editions du Seuil
- [Schoner 2000] B. Schoner. Probabilistic Characterization and Synthesis of Complex Driven Systems. Ph.D. Thesis, MIT. September 2000.
- [Schwartz 2004] Diemo Schwarz. Data-Driven Concatenative Sound Synthesis. PhD Thesis in Acoustics, Computer Science, Signal Processing Applied to Music, Université Paris 6 - Pierre et Marie Curie, January 20, 2004.

- [Serra 1998] Serra, X. "Musical sound modeling with sinusoids plus noise". In Roads, C., Pope, S., Picialli, A., De Poli, G. (eds.), *Musical signal processing*, 1998.
- [Serra and Bonada 1998] X. Serra and J. Bonada. "Sound Transformations based on the SMS High Level Attributes". *Proceedings of the Digital Audio Effects Workshop*, 1998.
- [Serres 1995] M. Serres. *Conversations on science, culture, and time / Michel Serres with Bruno Latour*. University of Michigan Press, 1995.
- [Schubert 1979] *Psychological Acoustics: Benchmark Papers in Acoustics, Volume 13*, edited by Earl D. Schubert, New York 1979
- [Schwarz 2005] Diemo Schwarz. *An Overview of Current Research in Concatenative Sound Synthesis*. *International Computer Music Conference (ICMC)*. Barcelona, September 2005.
- [Serra 1998] Serra, X. "Musical sound modeling with sinusoids plus noise". In Roads, C., Pope, S., Picialli, A., De Poli, G. (eds.), *Musical signal processing*, 1998.
- [Shlens 2005] Jon Shlens. *Tutorial on Principal Component Analysis*, 2005.
- [Scheirer 1998] Eric D. Scheirer. *The MPEG-4 structured audio standard*. *Proceedings of the IEEE ICASSP*, Seattle, May 1998

- [Scholkopf and Smola 2002] Bernhard Scholkopf and A. J. Smola: Learning with Kernels. MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, 2002.
- [Scholkopf et al. 1998] Scholkopf, B., Smola, A.J., Mller, K.-R. (1998). Nonlinear component analysis as a kernel eigenvalue problem. *Neural Computation*, 10:1299-1319.
- [Smith 1991] J. O. Smith III, "Viewpoints on the history of digital synthesis", Keynote paper, Proc Int. Computer Music Conf, Montreal, 1991.
- [Smola and Scholkopf 1998] A.J. Smola and B. Scholkopf. A tutorial on support vector regression. NeuroCOLT2 Technical Report NC2-TR-1998-030, 1998. <http://citeseer.ist.psu.edu/smola98tutorial.html>
- [Smola and Scholkopf 1998] Smola, A. J., & Scholkopf, B. (1998). A tutorial on support vector regression (NEUROCOLT Technical Report NC-TR-98-030). Royal Holloway College, London.
- [SMStools] SMStools application from MTG at University Pompeu Fabra. <http://iua-share.upf.es/wikis/clam/index.php/SMStoolsDetails>
- [Terhardt 1979] Terhardt, E. (1979). Calculating virtual pitch. *Hearing Research* 1, 155–182.
- [Ungvary and Vertegaal 2000] Ungvary, T. and Vertegaal, R. "Cognition and Physicality in Musical Cyberinstruments." In Wanderley, M. and Battier, M. (Eds.) *Trends in Gestural Control of*

- Music. IRCAM Electronic Books Series. Paris: IRCAM, 2000
- [Vanderveer 1979] N. Vanderveer, Ecological acoustics: Human perception of environmental sounds, Doctoral thesis, Dissertation Abstracts International, 1979.
- [Vercoe et al. 1998] Vercoe, Barry L., and William G. Gardner and Eric D. Scheirer. Structured Audio: Creation, Transmission, and Rendering of Parametric Sound Representations. Proc. IEEE 86:5 (May 1998), pp. 922-940
- [Vinet and Delalande 1999] Vinet, H. and F. Delalande (eds.). 1999. Interfaces homme-machine et creation musicale. Paris: Hermes Science Publications, 236 p
- [Vinet et al. 2002] Vinet, H. Herrera, P. Pachet, F. 2002. 'The CUIDADO Project' Proceedings of ISMIR 2002 - 3rd International Conference on Music Information Retrieval; Paris, France
- [Wanderley et al. 1998] M. Wanderley, N. Schnell, and J. B. Rovan. Escher-modeling and performing composed instruments in real-time. IEEE Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, 1998.
- [Wanderley and Depalle 1999] Wanderley, M.M. and P. Depalle, Controle Gestuel de la Synthese Sonore, in Interfaces Homme-Machine et Creation Musicale. 1999, Hermes Science Publications. p. 145-163

- [Wessel 1979] Wessel, D. L. (1979). Timbre space as a musical control structure. *Computer Music Journal*, 3 (2), 45–52.
- [Wessel et al. 1998] Wessel, David L., Cyril Drame, and Matthew Wright. “Removing the Time Axis from Spectral Model Analysis-based Additive Synthesis: Neural Networks versus Memory-Based Machine Learning.” *International Computer Music Conference*, 1998
- [Wessel and Wright 2001] Wessel, D. and Wright, M. Problems and Prospects for Intimate Musical Control of Computers. *Comp Mus J.* 26, 3 (2001), 11-22. 227
- [Wilson et al. 2003] Wilson, S., Gurevich, M., Verplank, B., and Stang, P. 2003. Microcontrollers in music HCI instruction: reflections on our switch to the Atmel AVR platform. In *Proceedings of the 2003 Conference on New interfaces For Musical Expression (Montreal, Quebec, Canada, May 22 - 24, 2003)*.
- [Wright et al. 1998] Wright, M., A. Chaudary, Freed, A., Wessel, D., Rodet, X., Virolle, D., Woehrmann, R., Serra, X.: New applications of the Sound Description Interchange Format. In: *Proc. ICMC-98, Ann Arbor, MI (1998)*
- [Wright et al. 2003] Wright, M., Freed, A., Momeni A.: *Open-Sound Control: State of the Art 2003*. <http://citeseer.ist.psu.edu/wright03opensound.html>

- [Xenakis 1971] I. Xenakis, *Formalized Music* (Bloomington, IN: Indiana Univ. Press, 1971)
- [Zicarelli 1998] Zicarelli, D. An Extensible Real-Time Signal Processing Environment for MAX. In *Proceedings of the 1998 International Computer Music Conference*. Ann Arbor, MI: International Computer Music Association, 463-466.
- [Zwicker and Scharf 1965] E. Zwicker and B. Scharf, "A model of loudness summation," *Psych. Rev.*, vol. 72, pp. 3–26, 1965.
- [Zwicker and Terhardt 1980] E. Zwicker and E. Terhardt, "Analytical expressions for critical band rate and critical bandwidth as a function of frequency," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, 68, pp. 1523-1525, 1980.